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Abstract:	<p>T3.1 Landscape report on software research, digital infrastructures, cybersecurity</p> <p>The intention of this task is to develop a first snapshot (and later refinement) of the "Landscape of software research, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity" first in Europe, but also looking at elements of the global dimension. The report will build upon existing knowledge and existing analysis, so as not to "reinvent the wheel", recognising that significant research and analysis have already been done, thus consolidating and expanding upon the work in the public domain. Furthermore, as this takes into account as well the aspects of digital infrastructures and cybersecurity, the extensive capabilities and networks included in the Cybersecurity Competence Centres Pilot Projects will also provide sources of information and knowledge which will be addressed in the deliverables resulting from this task. Given the importance of the landscape and the fact that all of the project partners are involved and can contribute, it is expected to cover the broadest approach in the European environment. And also, with the deep penetration of many of the project participants in the European software, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity eco-system (including active efforts within ECSO, EOS, the cPPP, SDOs and other), we can conclude that the interests of the stakeholders will be well represented in our work.</p>
Keyword List:	Landscape report, canvas for software, digital infrastructure and cybersecurity
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Terms and abbreviations

ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AEII	Agenda Estratégica de Investigación e Innovación
AENEAS	Association for European NanoElectronics ActivitieS
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	Association internationale sans but lucratif
ARTEMIS	Advanced Research & Technology for Embedded Intelligent Systems
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BoD	Board of Directors
COMPTIA	Computing Technology Industry Association
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECS	Electronic and Component Systems
ECSO	European Cyber Security Organisation
EOS	European Organisation for Security
EPoSS	European Technology Platform on Smart Systems
ETP	European Technology Platform
Eurofound	EU Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
IAP	Institution of Analysts and Programmers
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IF4IT	International Foundation for Information Technology
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
KDT	Key Digital Technologies
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
NEM Initiative	New European Media Initiative
NESSI	The Networked European Software and Services Initiative
OFE	Open Forum Europe

PB	Partnership Board
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
RSE	Research Software Engineers
SG	Secretary General
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SW	Software
SWEBOK	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge
SWForum.eu	European forum of the software research community
WAI-ARIA	Web Accessibility Initiative-Accessible Rich Internet Applications
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

This Landscape Report deliverable is the first in a series of two Reports, meant to describe the landscape surrounding the SWForum and the current existing and successful structures, which can provide model elements for the final form of the SWForum.

This deliverable does the following:

- 1) Describes the objective and the methodology (which includes questionnaires, interviews and research regarding existing models);
- 2) Shares the content and results of the questionnaires;
- 3) Presents the planning and structure for the interviews (to be included in the Landscape Report 2 deliverable due later in the project);
- 4) Explains the results of all of the existing models research, and
- 5) Provides conclusions and recommendations for SWForum to be successful, effective, efficient and sustainable.

The results of the questionnaire are included as an important element of this deliverable and these results are relevant in identifying key issues for the different categories of stakeholders. Furthermore, there is also a careful look at the different existing models which have elements that are also relevant for the stakeholder communities.

Finally, the conclusions and recommendations are based upon an in-depth understanding of not only the needs and desires of the stakeholders, but also with respect to the existing structures and elements.

It is very important to note that this deliverable is the first in a series of 2 Landscape reports with the second report due later in the SWForum.eu project lifecycle, while at the same time the development of the SWForum will be considered in detail in the next version of this report.

Also, it is key to recognise that the next version of this report will include a significant number of interviews and results from key stakeholders and individuals identified as being important for the future development of the SWForum.

And thus, this remains an evolutionary process with this current deliverable representing a key first step in understanding and defining the landscape around the SWForum.

1 Introduction, Structure of the Document, Objectives, and Methodology of the Effort

SWForum aims to achieve a sustainable support organisational structure which is both effective and efficient in addressing the needs of the software development community. As such, the Landscape Reports enable us to understand the current environment, the needs of the community and the opportunities to co-opt aspects which are important for the stakeholders.

This Landscape Report is the first version of the deliverable and is intended to share a first picture of the existing landscape based upon what has been developed and what is actually currently working well. A number of existing models that are coming from similar domains, but not necessarily exactly the same as SWForum, have been analysed. The intention is to start to build up a comprehensive picture of the successful approaches and structures that can be relevant for SWForum.

The document structure consists of 5 parts:

- 1) Chapter 1 describes the objective, structure and methodology for this deliverable.
- 2) Chapter 2 presents a canvas for SWForum’s landscape whilst taking into consideration existing references in the field of classification systems, taxonomies, standards, ranging from technologies and applications to practices, methodologies or concepts.
- 3) Chapter 3 highlights selected models with interesting services and approaches that could be relevant to SWForum.
- 4) Chapter 4 describes the stakeholder community, the questionnaire to users, the results and analysis of user feedback and the format of interviews which will be carried out.
- 5) Chapter 5 presents the conclusions and recommendations.

1.1 Objective

The objective of this deliverable is threefold: 1) to provide a first picture of the Landscape surrounding SWForum, 2) at the same time, to get initial inputs from the stakeholders and 3) to examine different existing organizational structures which could serve as models for the final form of the SWForum. Finally, first level conclusions and recommendations will be drawn from this analysis.

1.2 Methodology

Rather than trying to start from zero and “reinvent the wheel”, SWForum is striving to build upon what already exists, ensuring that we are not duplicating something from the existing landscape which could limit the success of SWForum, while at the same time being focused upon addressing the perceived needs of the most relevant stakeholders from the software community. This deliverable is specifically broader in remit than the Project Radar Landscape Analysis reports, deliverables D2.6 [1] and D2.7 [2], which will concentrate on the specific landscape of supported projects, and technically how they are distributed.

Thus, the methodology of the effort associated with this deliverable can be broken down into three clear parts:

- 1) A questionnaire for stakeholders in order to ascertain a sense of needs and requirements and what is already out there in terms of organizational and support structures.

- 2) A review of existing structures as a model and as an opportunity to identify key elements that are important for the efficiency and effectiveness of the organisation, as well as sustainability.
- 3) Interviews, which are being held with some of the most relevant stakeholders (although described within this deliverable, the actual interviews are not yet included in this first version of the Landscape Report, but rather will appear in the Final version due towards the end of the project).

The methodology also keeps in mind the important issues of sustainability, efficiency and effectiveness, while at the same time learning as much as possible from that which already exists in the current landscape.

This deliverable is designed to be as a complement to the deliverable D3.6 [3] in that in contrast D3.6 defines the strategy we aim at adopting for involving new fellows in the work of the SWForum and at the same time analyses different types of scientific and technical associations in the area of Information Technology with the purpose of this analysis in D3.6 to learn from other experiences and identify the best strategy to build a self-sustainable association.

This deliverable on the other hand is focused upon the basic needs of the stakeholders (hence the questionnaire) and with a focus upon looking at the services provided by existing models. With the second Landscape report of the series being the next evolution of this deliverable, it will include thus extensive interviews and results of those interviews with all of the key stakeholders as one of most important elements in the development of the SWForum.

2 A Canvas for Software, Digital Infrastructures and Cybersecurity Research

Information Technology is a broad and fast evolving knowledge field that includes different interdependent research and engineering topics, ranging from technologies and applications to practices, methodologies or concepts. It is a challenge to classify the whole knowledge field into meaningful categories to help the communication and a common understanding of their relationships as well as the dynamics of their research demands and evolution. Thus, the objective for this canvas is to be able to understand the division of the different elements of the knowledge field into clear and understandable categories for the purposes of this first Landscape report.

2.1 References in the current knowledge canvas

We address this by building a knowledge canvas reviewing some of the approaches that provide an IT representation in any of its main areas:

- ▣ ACM Computing Classification System;
- ▣ ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology;
- ▣ Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK);
- ▣ Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space;
- ▣ NESSI's SRIA;
- ▣ Electronic Component and Systems SRIA;
- ▣ ThoughtWorks technology radar;
- ▣ IF4IT's inventory of taxonomies and the specific IT discipline taxonomy;
- ▣ CompTIA's framework;
- ▣ Eurofound;
- ▣ PLANETIC AEII – Research and Innovation Strategy Agenda;
- ▣ The JRC CyberSecurity ATLAS and the JRC Taxonomy;

2.1.1 ACM Computing Classification System

The **ACM Computing Classification System** [4] is a taxonomy devised by the Association for Computing Machinery. The first version was created in 1964 and the current version in 2012. It is hierarchically structured in four levels. The first two levels of the hierarchy of all topics included in the 2012 version contain the elements described in Table 1.

It is important to note that SWForum has carefully examined the choice of taxonomies. In D2.4 [5], the requirements and description of taxonomies for SWForum is explained at length. In summary, it was concluded that ACM's Classification System would be adopted by SWForum.eu since its taxonomy is sufficiently broad to encompass tagging a wide range of projects.

Table 1: ACM Computing Classification System (first-two levels)

General and reference	Document types. Cross-computing tools and techniques.
Hardware	Printed circuit boards Communication hardware, interfaces and storage Integrated circuits Very large-scale integration design Power and energy

General and reference	Document types. Cross-computing tools and techniques.
	Electronic design automation Hardware validation Hardware test Robustness Emerging technologies
Computer systems organization	Architectures Embedded and cyber-physical systems Real-time systems Dependable and fault-tolerant systems and networks
Networks	Network architectures Network protocols Network components Network algorithms Network performance evaluation Network properties Network services Network types
Software and its engineering	Software organization and properties Software notations and tools Software creation and management
Theory of computation	Models of computation Formal languages and automata theory Computational complexity and cryptography Logic Design and analysis of algorithms Randomness, geometry and discrete structures Theory and algorithms for application domains Semantics and reasoning
Mathematics of computing	Discrete mathematics Probability and statistics Mathematical software Information theory Mathematical analysis Continuous mathematics
Information systems	Data management systems Information storage systems Information systems applications World Wide Web Information retrieval
Security and privacy	Cryptography Formal methods and theory of security Security services Intrusion/anomaly detection and malware mitigation Security in hardware Systems security Network security Database and storage security Software and application security

General and reference	Document types. Cross-computing tools and techniques.
	Human and societal aspects of security and privacy
Human-centered computing	Human computer interaction (HCI) Interaction design Collaborative and social computing Ubiquitous and mobile computing Visualization Accessibility
Computing methodologies	Symbolic and algebraic manipulation Parallel computing methodologies Artificial intelligence Machine learning Modelling and simulation Computer graphics Distributed computing methodologies Concurrent computing methodologies
Applied computing	Electronic commerce Enterprise computing Physical sciences and engineering Life and medical sciences Law, social and behavioral sciences Computer forensics Arts and humanities Computers in other domains Operations research Education Document management and text processing
Social and professional topics	Professional topics Computing / technology policy User characteristics

2.1.2 ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology

The **International Organization for Standardization (ISO)/International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Joint Technical Committee (JTC) 1** [6] is an organization established by the ISO and IEC that is responsible for international standardization in the field of IT and Information and Communication Technology (ICT). It has currently published 3,257 standards. The development of these standards is carried out by the following 22 Sub Committees and 4 Working Groups (WGs) directly under JTC 1, most of the them with several working groups, each of which deal with a particular field (list as of June 2021).

Table 2: ISO/IEC JTC- 22 Sub Committees and 4 Working Groups (WGs)

REFERENCE	TITLE
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 2	Coded character sets
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6	Telecommunications and information exchange between systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7	Software and systems engineering

REFERENCE	TITLE
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17	Cards and security devices for personal identification
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 22	Programming languages, their environments and system software interfaces
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 23	Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 24	Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25	Interconnection of information technology equipment
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 28	Office equipment
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29	Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 31	Automatic identification and data capture techniques
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32	Data management and interchange
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 34	Document description and processing languages
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 35	User interfaces
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 36	Information technology for learning, education and training
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37	Biometrics
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38	Cloud computing and distributed platforms
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 39	Sustainability, IT and data centres
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 40	IT service management and IT governance
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41	Internet of things and digital twin
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	Artificial intelligence
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 11	Smart cities
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 12	3D Printing and scanning
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 13	Trustworthiness
ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 14	Quantum Computing

For example, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7 develops and facilitates standards within the field of engineering of software products and systems, with the following working groups:

Table 3: ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7 - WGs in the field of engineering of software products & systems

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 7 WG	Title of Working Group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 2	System software documentation
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 4	Tools and environment
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 6	Software Product and System Quality
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 7	Life cycle management
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 10	Process assessment
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 19	Techniques for Specifying IT Systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 20	Software and systems bodies of knowledge and professionalization
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 21	Information technology asset management
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 22	Vocabulary validation
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 24	Systems and software standards for Very Small Entities
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 26	Software testing
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 29	Agile and DevOps
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7/WG 42	Architecture

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 [7] develops and facilitates standards within the field of Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection, with the following working groups:

Table 4: ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 - WGs in the field of cybersecurity and privacy protection

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG	Title of Working Group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 1	Information security management systems
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 2	Cryptography and security mechanisms
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3	Security evaluation, testing and specification
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 4	Security controls and services
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5	Identity management and privacy technologies
Joint ISO/TC 307 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG	Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies and IT Security techniques

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 [8] develops and facilitates standards within the field of Cloud Computing, Distributed Platforms, and the application of these technologies, with the following working groups:

Table 5: ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 - WG in the field of cloud computing

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 38 WG	Title of Working Group
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/WG 3	Cloud Computing Fundamentals (CCF)
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38/WG 5	Data in cloud computing and related technologies

2.1.3 Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK)

SWEBOK, Software Engineering Body of Knowledge [9], is a guide created by the Software Engineering Coordinating Committee and promoted by IEEE Computer Society. It defines the software engineering knowledge that practitioners should have after four years of practice, that is, it is mainly intended for software engineering methodologies and practices. The current version v3 was approved in 2013 and has the following 15 knowledge areas:

- ☐ Software requirements
- ☐ Software design
- ☐ Software construction
- ☐ Software testing
- ☐ Software maintenance
- ☐ Software configuration management
- ☐ Software engineering management
- ☐ Software engineering process
- ☐ Software engineering models and methods
- ☐ Software quality
- ☐ Software engineering professional practice
- ☐ Software engineering economics
- ☐ Computing foundations
- ☐ Mathematical foundations
- ☐ Engineering foundations

2.1.4 Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space

The actions under the **Digital, Industry and Space cluster of the Horizon Europe Programme** [10] will support during 2021 and 2022 key enabling technologies that are strategically important for Europe’s industrial future. They are not a classification of knowledge areas of IT subjects; both Destination 3, “world leading data and computing technologies”, and Destination 4, “digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the green deal”, will directly support the research in the following topics that are related to ICT:

- ☐ Technologies and solutions for compliance, privacy preservation, green and responsible data operations;
- ☐ Technologies for data management;
- ☐ Technologies and solutions for data trading, monetizing, exchange and interoperability;
- ☐ Extreme data mining, aggregation and analytics technologies and solutions;
- ☐ Methods for exploiting data and knowledge for extremely precise outcomes (analysis, prediction, decision support), reducing complexity and presenting insights in understandable way;
- ☐ Future European platforms for the Edge: Meta Operating Systems;
- ☐ Cognitive Cloud: AI-enabled computing continuum from Cloud to Edge;
- ☐ Programming tools for decentralised intelligence and swarms;

- ▣ AI, Data and Robotics for the Green Deal;
- ▣ AI, Data and Robotics at work;
- ▣ AI, Data and Robotics for Industry optimisation (including production and services);
- ▣ Pushing the limit of robotics cognition;
- ▣ Open source for cloud-based services;
- ▣ Pushing the limit of physical intelligence and performance;
- ▣ Strengthening the quantum software ecosystem for quantum computing platforms;
- ▣ Large scale quantum simulation platform technologies;
- ▣ Quantum Internet;
- ▣ Quantum encryption and future quantum network technologies;
- ▣ Open testing and experimentation for quantum technologies in Europe.

2.1.5 NESSI's SRIA

The **European Technology Platform dedicated to Software, Services and Data, NESSI**, published its last version of the SRIA in 2017 [11] with a systematic review of the technological challenges to be addressed to build digital systems that need to be distributed and ubiquitous, trusted and sustainable and exhibit new levels of intelligence. In its vision of a digital society and economy, software is a key asset that still requires solving tremendous significant challenges such as:

- ▣ The increased heterogeneity in infrastructure, communication, policies, SLAs;
- ▣ Security, privacy and trust concerns;
- ▣ Non-functional aspects such as robustness, availability, recoverability, performance;
- ▣ The support for distributed processing, and the trade-off between autonomy and global control;
- ▣ Dynamic evolution (AI, machine learning, self-adaptation);
- ▣ End-user interaction and end-user programming; and
- ▣ Cyber physical systems eventually 'merging' humans and machines.

NESSI considers four dimensions that characterize digital systems of all kinds: Digital Infrastructures, Software Technologies, Data and Services. Their related trends lead to a continuous flow of opportunity, based on software and service innovation, to build a better Digital Information Society and Economy.

Figure 2-1: Innovations for the Digital Information Society and Economy. (Source: adapted from the NESSI’s SRIA 2017)

Using the four Dimensions (Digital Infrastructures, Software Technologies, Data and Services), NESSI addresses the research and innovation challenges according to three major characteristics of modern computing systems: Physical/Embedded/Distributed Computing, Secure/Trustworthy/Sustainable Computing, and Smart/Cognitive Computing.

Table 6: NESSI - Research and Innovation Challenges

Characteristics Dimensions	Physical Embedded Distributed Computing	Secure Trustworthy Sustainable Computing	Smart Cognitive Computing
A – Digital Infrastructures	Computing Continuum	Dynamic policies and behaviours	Self-adaptable infrastructures
B - Software Technologies	Full-stack software	Programming policies	Self-aware programs
C - Data	Data everywhere	Built-in protection of assets and actors	Knowledge and insight for decisions
D - Services	Software defined sectors	Regulation in societies of services	Digital business agents

2.1.6 Electronic Component and Systems - SRIA

The 2021 version of the **Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (ECS-SRIA) of the Electronic and Component Systems** [12] has been jointly developed by members of three industry associations: AENEAS (Association for European NanoElectronics Activities), ARTEMIS-IA (Advanced Research & Technology for Embedded Intelligent Systems) and EPoSS (European Technology Platform on Smart Systems). Its scope is very wide, ranging from transistors within silicon chips acting as individual electrical switches for integration in smart systems, up to global System of Systems (SoS) performing complex cognitive tasks and interacting with numerous humans and machines over a wide geographical spread. Its structure is composed of four “Foundational Technology Layers” complemented by four “Cross-Sectional Technology sections” and six key Application areas. ECS’s fields could be considered as the foundations of Software Systems and the digital society; however, some of the topics are well aligned to the SWForum’s intended domains. For instance, regarding one of the Foundation Technology Layers, the “Embedded software developments and software technologies” layer, it points out the following breakthroughs for (embedded) software innovation:

- ❑ Improved multidisciplinary embedded software architecting and design;
- ❑ Increased efficiency and an effective product innovation process;
- ❑ Enabled adaptable systems by adaptable embedded software;
- ❑ Improved system integration and testing;
- ❑ Embedded software, and embedded data analytics and AI, to enable system health monitoring, diagnostics and preventive maintenance;
- ❑ Data privacy and data integrity;
- ❑ Model-based embedded software design and engineering as the basis for managing complexity in SoS;
- ❑ Embedded software architecting/design for (systems) qualities, including reliability, trust, safety, security, performance, installable, diagnosable, sustainability, re-use;
- ❑ Upgradability and extending useful life.

And “Quality, Reliability, Safety and Cybersecurity” is one of the four “Cross-Sectional Technology sections” that is also linked to the SWForum’s knowledge fields.

2.1.7 ThoughtWorks technology radar

The **ThoughtWorks technology radar** [13] captures quarterly the output of an advisory board regarding software and IT technologies and techniques using two categorizing elements: quadrants and rings. The quadrants represent four different kinds of themes (which they refer to as “blips”): techniques, platforms, tools and languages & frameworks. The rings indicate what stage in an adoption lifecycle they think they should be worth considering: hold, assess, trial or adopt. The radar provides the ThoughtWorks’ opinion of what is happening in the IT business with a focus on available tools and capabilities.

The Cyberwatching.eu Project Radar was an adaptation of the ThoughtWorks Technology Radar. SWForum will continue to use and further develop the Cyberwatching Project Radar, as explained in [14]”, with the intention to continue to develop, maintain and operate the Project Radar adapting it to the requirements of SWForum. The utilisation of visual analytics techniques within the radar and the taxonomy, filters and methods are described in D2.4 “Project Radar Taxonomies” [5].

2.1.8 IF4IT’s inventory of taxonomies and the specific IT discipline taxonomy

The **International Foundation for Information Technology (IF4IT)**, provides a large inventory of taxonomies; among them, the **IT discipline taxonomy** [15] which is a flat taxonomy covering a

broad range of more than 1,000 key IT Disciplines that are used IT organizations and professionals to help manage (define, structure, organize, and understand) various forms of Data, Information, and Knowledge. Those items could be understood under the context of SWForum as “software products” (or software applications).

2.1.9 Computing Technology Industry Association (CompTIA)’s framework

The **Computing Technology Industry Association’s IT framework** [16] is composed of four basic building blocks: infrastructure, development, security and data.

Figure 2-2: The four building blocks of the CompTIA’s framework. (Source: CompTIA).

The Infrastructure establishes the foundation for the rest of the IT architecture, providing the backbone for installing applications and keeping them running, as well as supporting users. Critical areas within Infrastructure in this IT framework are cloud computing, networking, storage, server administration, Internet of Things (IoT), mobile device management, help desk or Linux.

The Development block includes the building and customization of applications that are either used internally or by external customers. Critical areas under this building block are user experience, quality assurance, Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML), mobile development and DevOps (Development & Operation).

Security ensures the proper behaviour of infrastructures and applications against external attacks or internal risks. Critical areas within Security are cybersecurity analytics, privacy, risk analysis, compliance, cybersecurity metrics, workforce education or penetration testing.

Data is the abstract component to be managed by the rest of IT building blocks. Critical areas within data are database administration, predictive analytics, data visualization, data governance and blockchain / distributed ledger technologies.

Potential emerging technologies that may impact the IT framework evolution, according to CompTIA’s reports, are Artificial Intelligence, IoT, 5G, serverless computing, edge computing, 3D printing, quantum computing, robotics, robotic process automation, biometrics, virtual reality, self-driving or autonomous vehicles, distributed ledger / blockchain, containers, augmented reality, SD WAN, drones, volumetric displays and digital twins.

2.1.10 Eurofound

The **EU Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions (Eurofound)**, studied the implications of eight game-changing technologies for work, employment and employment relations. In the associated research report, “Game-changing technologies: Transforming production and employment in Europe” [17], Eurofound differentiates three digital vectors of change that are influencing work and employment in Europe as of mid-2019: Automation, Digitisation and Coordination by Platforms.

Figure 2-3: Digital vectors of change of Eurofound research report on game-changing technologies.
(Source: own elaboration).

2.1.11 PLANETIC AEII – Research and Innovation Strategy Agenda

PLANETIC, the Spanish Technological Platform for the promotion and dissemination of ICT has developed in 2019 its fifth version (in Spanish) of the **PLANETIC's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (AEII – SRIA)** [18]. PLANETIC's mission is to promote innovation in the Spanish digital technology sector through a global and integrated vision of these interrelated technologies. One of its functions is to identify the challenges in terms of research and innovation in the medium and long term of the different thematic areas covered by the platform, aligned with the challenges identified in other similar fora and the European Research Area.

The current version of the SRIA uses an enhanced map of the ICT technological domains which were defined in previous versions. These domains have been grouped into three areas, Software Systems, Integrated Intelligence and Digital Interaction, with three domains each, and a transversal one, Data management and analytics, configuring a set of 10 domains in total (see Figure 2-3):

- *Technologies that are directly related to the omnipresence of Software Systems.* Most of the functions that are required by new digital services or those provided by applications, goods and products in an intelligent environment are implemented using software. It is then essential the optimal production and operation of perfect software. Technology development and innovation is needed to produce, deploy and operate these high-quality, competitive software systems. Code that must be efficient, reliable, robust, fault tolerant, reusable and well done, as well as the mechanisms, techniques and tools to be developed and deployed into operation in almost any IT infrastructure in time, with the highest quality and at the lowest cost. In addition to conventional computing systems, a new paradigm is emerging with quantum computing that will pose a set of new challenges both in relation to current systems (for example, their ability to protect current systems against the capacities of these new paradigms - decryption, for instance) and to future systems: how are they programmed, how are they operated, etc. This area includes the *Software Engineering* domain, the *IT infrastructures* domain and the *Cybersecurity and Safety* domain.
- *Technologies related to the integration of intelligence into the environment.* With the technification of almost any product or device (from tiny tags to large physical systems), our environment is becoming more sophisticated in our personal life, at home, in the business environment, in infrastructures, etc. Software systems provide the intelligence to this environment, enabling it to incorporate new capacities for perception, processing, inference, learning, acting or interacting with other systems or

people. This area includes the *Embedded Processing and Communication* domain, the *Sensing and Actuating* domain, and the *Cognitive and Intelligent Systems, Control and Robotics* domain. The new digital technologies thus contribute to creating products, systems and solutions with intelligent behaviour based on components, electronic systems, software (embedded or not), and communications. The advances of micro and nanotechnologies in the electronic field provide the substrate for the basis of this chain, enabling the interrelation between the physical and digital world, and making it possible for these capabilities to be extended to practically every product.

- ▣ *Technologies that are related to the digital interaction.* Digital technologies are radically transforming the way we interact, communicate, inform and learn, entertain or carry out transactions of any kind. We are experiencing a progressive digitization and dematerialization of all kinds of media and physical substrates of information-based paradigms, such as books, maps, records, coins... At the same time, we advance towards a more natural, richer and ubiquitous form of digital interaction. This area includes in the SRIA the *Content Management* domain, the *Social and Mobile* domain and the *Interaction Technologies* domain.
- ▣ As a result of the digitalization of processes, products and services, the digital universe generates huge amounts of information and data. The *Data analytics* transversal domain, from a more mathematical perspective, seeks to extract value from these volumes of data, infer hypotheses and help in decision making.

The following map allows for the visualization of the previous ten domains and their interrelationships grouped into three, plus one transversal, areas.

Figure 2-4: The IT domains of the PLANETIC's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. (Source: adapted from PLANETIC).

Compared to other representation methods, PLANETIC’s approach introduces an important and original element for understanding IT research needs. The map helps correlate technologies or knowledge themes and where IT professionals or specialists of these themes are mainly required in the industry. As represented in Figure 2-4, the research themes that are under the three domains of the Software Systems area are the core competences of professionals of the IT industry: software providers, application developers or IT service providers. Research themes that are under the Ubiquitous Intelligence area are core for IT professionals of the manufacturing industry of almost all sectors, from telecom equipment to medical devices, in order to create *smart* systems. The similar applies for the third area with professionals of companies from the service industry, like communications, information, entertainment, education, retail, e-tourism, e-Administration... as service interactions are progressively provided by digital means. Finally, Data is considered a transversal area, as data-specialized professionals are required in all previous markets and segments.

Figure 2-5: Correspondence of PLANETIC’s IT domains and main industries working in these domains. (Source: adapted from PLANETIC).

2.1.12 The JRC CyberSecurity ATLAS

The European Cybersecurity Atlas is a knowledge management platform that maps, categorises, visualises, and analyses information on cybersecurity expertise in Europe. Its goal is to foster the collaboration between European cybersecurity experts in support of the EU Digital Strategy. The European Cybersecurity Atlas and EU cybersecurity taxonomy supports European Regulation COM/2018/630 [19], which calls for the establishment of a European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre and Network of National Coordination Centres [20].

The primary goals of the Atlas platform are to:

- ▣ facilitate the establishment of a community of practice
- ▣ help identify with whom to collaborate on future projects
- ▣ map the competencies of Europe in various cybersecurity domains
- ▣ act as a knowledge management tool for the future European Cybersecurity Competence Centre
- ▣ raise the visibility of participants within the cybersecurity community and beyond

- ▣ better coordinate European R&D efforts in cybersecurity
- ▣ contribute to shaping the strategic orientations of EU programmes funding cybersecurity research, technology and capabilities
- ▣ provide relevant input to cybersecurity policymaking in Europe
- ▣ provide awareness of the cybersecurity community
- ▣ support the European Commission on managing work programmes and allocation of funds.

The main benefits for organisations and researchers in providing their information to the Atlas platform are:

- ▣ **Networking:** the platform provides an opportunity to enlarge the research network and get in contact with relevant peers across Europe.
- ▣ **Visibility and influence:** the participation in the platform improves the organisation visibility allowing it to be taken into consideration by the EC and cybersecurity community in EU policies, programmes, events, and sectorial activities.
- ▣ Furthermore, students, job seekers, and market analysts are a few important users expected to use the Atlas as a reference point for cybersecurity expertise in Europe.

Key stakeholders include:

- ▣ *Cybersecurity Competence Community:* this community consists of cybersecurity stakeholders, such as research institutions, companies and actors from the public sector. Members of the Community will share information with the Competence Centre, which will become a focal point of their activities.
- ▣ *Network of National Coordination Centres:* Each Member State will nominate one National Coordination Centre, which will serve as a contact point between the members of the Community and the Competence Centre. The National Coordination Centres will also facilitate participation in cross-border projects and create synergies with activities at national and regional level.
- ▣ *The European Cybersecurity Industrial, Technology and Research Competence Centre:* this centre will coordinate the Network and support the Community by providing common access to cybersecurity expertise. Governed by representatives from Member States and the European Commission, it will play a key role in executing the Digital Europe and Horizon Europe programmes.

2.2 A Canvas Proposal for SWForum’s Landscape

This chapter presents the methodology to develop SWForum’s Landscape based on existing references as described in Section 2.1.

2.2.1 The IT Technologies canvas approach

The proposal for a canvas to represent the research landscape is to use a reorganized version of the ACM’s Computing Classification System, with focus on the three main areas of SWForum, namely, “Software Systems”, “IT infrastructure” and “Cybersecurity”, which are mainly composed of the following components of the first two levels of the taxonomy (see Table 7). As described previously both this analysis and the project radar are utilising the same taxonomy (D2.5 “Project radar technical roadmap”) to ensure alignment between this the larger software landscape beyond just supported projects and the radar.

Table 7: SWForum themes and ACM Taxonomy

SWForum themes	ACM's level 1	ACM's level 2
Software Engineering	Software and its engineering	Software organization and properties Software notations and tools Software creation and management
	Computer systems organization	Real-time systems
	Computing methodologies	Parallel computing methodologies Distributed computing methodologies Concurrent computing methodologies
IT Infrastructures	Computer systems organization	Architectures Embedded and cyber-physical systems Dependable and fault-tolerant systems and networks
	Information systems	Data management systems Information storage systems Information systems applications World Wide Web Information retrieval
Cybersecurity	Security and privacy	Cryptography Formal methods and theory of security Security services Intrusion/anomaly detection and malware mitigation Security in hardware Systems security Network security Database and storage security Software and application security Human and societal aspects of security and privacy
	Theory of computation	Models of computation Formal languages and automata theory Computational complexity and cryptography Logic Design and analysis of algorithms Randomness, geometry and discrete structures Theory and algorithms for application domains Semantics and reasoning
	Mathematics of computing	Discrete mathematics Probability and statistics Mathematical software Information theory Mathematical analysis Continuous mathematics
	Networks	Network algorithms Network services
	Computing methodologies (other)	Symbolic and algebraic manipulation Artificial intelligence Machine learning Modelling and simulation Computer graphics

SWForum themes	ACM's level 1	ACM's level 2
	Human-centered computing	Human computer interaction (HCI) Interaction design Collaborative and social computing Ubiquitous and mobile computing Visualization Accessibility
	Applied computing	Electronic commerce Enterprise computing Physical sciences and engineering Life and medical sciences Law, social and behavioral sciences Computer forensics Arts and humanities Computers in other domains Operations research Education Document management and text processing

2.2.2 SWForum's IT Technology canvas correspondence with other approaches

The proposed IT Technology canvas and its items have direct correspondence with the items of some of the previously examined taxonomies and classifications. The following table provides this comparison.

Table 8: SWForum’s Information Technology canvas based on a comparison of existing classifications/taxonomies

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
Software Engineering	<p>Computer systems organization - Real-time systems.</p> <p>Software and its engineering - Software organization and properties / Software notations and tools / Software creation and management.</p> <p>Computing methodologies - Symbolic and algebraic manipulation / Parallel computing methodologies / Distributed computing</p>	<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 7 - Software and systems engineering.</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 22 - Programming languages, their environments and system software interfaces.</p>	<p>Software requirements, design, construction, testing, maintenance, configuration management, engineering management, engineering process, engineering models and methods, quality, engineering professional practice, engineering economics, Computing foundations, Mathematical</p>	<p>Full-stack software.</p> <p>Programming policies / Policies by design.</p> <p>Self-aware programs / World-aware programs.</p>	<p>Future European platforms for the Edge: Meta Operating Systems.</p> <p>Programming tools for decentralised intelligence and swarms.</p> <p>Open source for cloud-based services.</p> <p>Strengthening the quantum software ecosystem for quantum computing platforms.</p>	<p>Infrastructure - Linux.</p> <p>Development - DevOps (Development & Operation).</p>	<p>Software Engineering - Software production and commissioning / software quality / programming languages.</p>

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
	methodologies / Concurrent computing methodologies		foundations, Engineering foundations.		Large scale quantum simulation platform technologies. Open testing and experimentation for quantum technologies in Europe.		
IT Infrastructures	Computer systems organization – Architectures. Information systems - Data management systems / Information storage systems / Information systems applications /	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 - Cloud computing and distributed platforms. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 39 - Sustainability, IT and data centres. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 40 - IT service management and IT governance.		Computing continuum Dynamic policies. Self-adaptable infrastructures.	Cognitive Cloud: AI-enabled computing continuum from Cloud to Edge.	Infrastructure - cloud computing, networking, storage, server administration / quality assurance.	IT Infrastructures - Continuum computing / parallel computing / High-performance computing.

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
	World Wide Web / Information retrieval.						
Cybersecurity	Computer systems organization - Dependable and fault-tolerant systems and networks. Security and privacy Cryptography - Formal methods and theory of security / Security services / Intrusion/anomaly detection and malware mitigation / Security in hardware / Systems security / Network security /	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17 - Cards and security devices for personal identification. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 – Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection. ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 13 – Trustworthiness. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37 – Biometrics.		Built-in protection of assets and actors.	Quantum encryption and future quantum network technologies.	Security - cybersecurity analytics / privacy / risk analysis / compliance / cybersecurity metrics / workforce education / penetration testing. Data - database administration / blockchain / distributed ledger technologies.	Cybersecurity and Safety - Safe systems design / Cybersecurity / Algorithm, encryption and control.

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
	Database and storage security / Software and application security / Human and societal aspects of security and privacy.						
	Computer systems organization - Embedded and cyber-physical systems.	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6 - Telecommunications and information exchange between systems. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 - Internet of things and digital twin.		Computing continuum	Quantum Internet.	Infrastructure - Internet of Things (IoT).	Embedded processing and communication – components and subsystems / communication protocols.
		ISO/IEC JTC 1/WG 12 - 3D Printing and scanning.					Sensing & Actuation - new materials and devices / design tools /

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
							conscience of the environment / energy issues.
	Computing methodologies - Artificial intelligence / Machine learning / Modelling and simulation.	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 - Artificial intelligence.		Digital business agents.	AI, Data and Robotics for the Green Deal. AI, Data and Robotics at work. AI, Data and Robotics for Industry optimisation (including production and services). Pushing the limit of robotics cognition. Pushing the limit of physical	Development - Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML).	Cognitive and Intelligent systems, control and robotics – cognitive and intelligent systems / control and robotic technologies.

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
					intelligence and performance.		
		<p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 23 - Digitally recorded media for information interchange and storage.</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 24 - Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation.</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29 - Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information.</p>					Content Management – Audio-visual & gaming / VR-AR-MR / Semantics / service architectures.
	Human-centered computing - Collaborative and social computing /					Development - mobile development.	Social & Mobile – personal architectures / social

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
	Ubiquitous and mobile computing.						technologies / context technologies.
	Human-centered computing - Human computer interaction (HCI) / Interaction design / Visualization / Accessibility.	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 35 - User interfaces.				Development - user experience.	Interaction systems – Human-system interaction / natural & emphatic interaction.
	Mathematics of computing - Discrete mathematics / Probability and statistics / Mathematical software / Information theory / Mathematical analysis /	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 32 - Data management and interchange.		Data everywhere. Knowledge and insight for decisions.	Technologies and solutions for compliance, privacy preservation, green and responsible data operations. Technologies for data management.	Data - predictive analytics / data visualization / data governance.	Data Analytics – data analysis methods / data visualization & interaction / data modelling.

SWForum’s IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI’s SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA’s framework (2).	PLANETIC’s SRIA (2)
	Continuous mathematics.				<p>Technologies and solutions for data trading, monetizing, exchange and interoperability.</p> <p>Extreme data mining, aggregation and analytics technologies and solutions.</p> <p>Methods for exploiting data and knowledge for extremely precise outcomes (analysis, prediction, decision support), reducing complexity and</p>		

SWForum's IT landscape themes (1)	ACM Computing Classification System (2).	ISO/IEC JTC 1 Information Technology (2).	Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK).	NESSI's SRIA (2).	Horizon Europe Programme, Cluster Digital, Industry and Space (3).	CompTIA's framework (2).	PLANETIC's SRIA (2)
					presenting insights in understandable way.		

Note (1): in shadow, the three SWForum main areas: software, IT infrastructure and cybersecurity.

Note (2): some examples included.

Note (3): from work programme 2021-2022.

3 IT Landscape Structure

3.1 IT Landscape trends and drivers

The previous canvas has the objective of depicting the Information Technology (IT) space where the research activities under these three pillar technologies (software, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity) can be located and understood within the context of the global development of the digital economy and society.

The development of these IT pillar technologies is made possible by a series of enabling technologies with direct impact on computing, communication, storage or sensing/actuating capabilities and performance. Their research orientation is defined by the demands and requirements of a society that is becoming digital in almost every aspect of daily life, from leisure to work. As more and more business and organizational processes are assisted or automated with software applications and tools, software is becoming increasingly pervasive in almost every product of the human environment, from (*smart*) tags to large physical (*smart*) infrastructures. The provision of services, including information, communication, education, shopping, payment, health, or civic participation services, to give some examples, are increasingly supported through digital channels.

Figure 3-1: Context of the IT pillars within the digital space. (Source: PLANETIC)

The three pillar IT technologies are inside a *push-pull sandwich* (Figure 3-1) between the enabling layer, on one hand, and the demanding layer, on the other. Their development is conditioned by a demanding context where software is ubiquitous in any component of the environment (both in those *IT-native* components that are used for supporting most of business and personal processes as well as in any component of any type of the surrounding environment that is progressively incorporating software) and where interactions are supported, enhanced or just directly provided by digital means. Ubiquitous intelligence and digital service provision are the two “big drivers” of the digital economy and society:

- ❏ An environment with ubiquitous intelligence which is symbiotic with other intelligent systems and with people; “symbiotic” means the mutually beneficiary relationship among systems and of those with people.
- ❏ A digital provision experience that is indistinguishable from the physical or “real” experience or even richer.

At the same time, there is a wide set of constraints that prevents moving forward at greater speed in this digital development. The limited ability to absorb these fast developments, the lack of specialized talent to develop solutions or the difficulties to capitalize on the investment of digital developments are some of these restrictions.

The **vision** is to build “perfect” software systems that are produced & operated “at no cost”.

Due to these considerations, even if the research rationale of these three pillar technologies has become highly dynamic and complex, the desired vision has a very simple formulation: *Perfect software systems that are produced & operated at no cost*. “Perfect” means free from faults, secure, resistant, resilient, able to run

everywhere, etc. “at no cost” means that the production, deployment, and operation of software systems are optimized and automated with regards of the need of human resources or natural resources (e.g., energy, waste).

The priorities for the research and innovation in each of the knowledge domains can be identified for their contribution to the ideal vision. The challenges to adapt to this purpose are:

- ❏ To increase the robustness, security, resilience and reliability of software products and applications.
- ❏ To facilitate the execution over a continuum computing platform.
- ❏ To facilitate and automate programming, even by less or non-expert users.
- ❏ To allow for the production and exploitation of software almost simultaneously, reducing the delay between production and operation in a continuous life cycle.
- ❏ To move towards dynamic, adaptable, and evolutionary forms of execution.
- ❏ To adapt systems to the new paradigms that are appearing, such as quantum computing.

3.2 Current models

A number of models exist currently and although they may come from similar domains, there are also models coming from quite different domains which represent interesting services and approaches that could actually be quite relevant for SWForum, and thus there is a very relevant diversity represented here. It should be noted that not every model and example will be addressed, but opportunities do exist for using concepts from many of these in our SWForum approach.

D3.6 [3] also presents a landscape of associations (many of which are listed below), but the analysis in D3.6 is given from the perspective of governance structure and business model whereas the analysis below examines the structure from the perspective of type of organization and the services offered.

In contrast, the purpose of the D3.6 deliverable is twofold. On the one side, it defines the strategy we aim at adopting for involving new fellows in the work of the Forum. On the other side, it presents the analysis performed by the SWForum.eu consortium of various types of scientific and technical associations in the area of Information Technology. The purpose of this analysis in D3.6 is to learn from other experiences and identify the best strategy to build a self-sustainable association.

For this deliverable we have selected the most relevant models, which have the focus upon services important for the stakeholders. While at the same time these models have existing approaches, which can be key elements for the future of the SWForum.

3.2.1 AI-Alliance

AI-Alliance	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	A community of multi-stakeholders forum
DATE OF CREATION	June 2018
MISSION STATEMENT	The forum's initial scope was the provision of feedback to the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI HLEG), which was appointed by the European Commission to assist with policy development. The initial goal of the AI Alliance is now extended, and members can now contribute with discussions, documents, and debates into the policy aspects demanded by the European Commission.
STRUCTURE	Members approved that can access the AI Alliance platform can interact with the AI HLEG which functions as the Steering Group.
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	Research topics dealing with Artificial Intelligence, including: Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI, safety and liability implications of Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things and robotics, Biometric identification, AI Conformity assessment, standards and high-risk AI applications, AI tools to fight the COVID-pandemic , Uptake of AI in the public sectors, Advanced automation through AI.
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the policy-making process of the European Commission • Participate in discussions with each other and the experts of the AI HLEG in a dedicated forum. • Provide feedback on specific questions and on draft documents prepared by the AI HLEG under a dedicated section. • Organisation of networking events and with the • Access official documents on AI • Contribute reports and papers • Self-assessment of AI systems through an specific methodology
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	Only one, the AI HLEG.
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	The European AI Alliance is an online forum with over 4000 members representing academia, business and industry, civil society, EU citizens and policymakers. Members include representatives from academia, civil society and industry. Some members individuals from the following organizations: ANSII, IEEE, Zalando, IBM, Airbus, SAP, Bosch, and more.

AI-Alliance	
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF THE MEMBERS	Mainly European but there are also international members.
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	NA
MEMBERSHIP FEES	There is no membership fee to be part of the AI Alliance platform.
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	NA
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	1 conference, white papers, annual European AI Alliance Assembly.
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE	In growth
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	The European Commission.

3.2.2 Big Data Value association (BDVA)

Big Data Value association (BDVA)	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	Not-for-profit organisation. Is the private part of the Big Data Value PPP ¹ .
DATE OF CREATION	The BDV PPP was launched in 2014.
MISSION STATEMENT	<p>The mission of the BDVA is to develop the Innovation Ecosystem that will enable the data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe delivering maximum economic and societal benefit, and, achieving and sustaining Europe's leadership on Big Data Value creation and Artificial Intelligence.</p> <p>In 2020 BDVA has expanded the scope and breadth of activities and has become BDVA/DAIRO, which stands for Data, AI and Robotics. For simplicity reasons, we will use BDVA.</p>
STRUCTURE	The General Assembly (GA) is conformed by all the BDVA members (only Full members have voting rights). BDVA GA approves the general policy of the Association on the basis of proposals of the Board of Directors and gives recommendations to the Board of Directors for its application. The Board of Directors (BoD) is selected by the General Assembly (2-year mandate). The Board of Directors is in charge of reaching the objectives of the Association. It follows the resolutions, instructions and recommendations adopted by the General Assembly. The GA also elects the President, Vice President(s) and

¹ The public part is the European Commission

Big Data Value association (BDVA)	
	Treasurer. The Partnership Board (PB) is the monitoring body of the cPPP composed by a group of selected directors of the Board, and representatives of the European Commission. The Secretary General (SG) is responsible for the day-to-day administrative management of the Association with the support of the Deputy Secretary General and BDVA Secretariat.
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	<p>From the latest SRIA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Management • Data Processing Architectures • Data Analytics • Data Visualisation and User Interaction • Data Protection • Big Data Standardisation • Engineering and DevOps for Big Data
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stronger access to agenda of data and AI R&I policies, regulation and standardisation • Access to strategic communities working on AI and Big Data R&I in Europe and worldwide • Additional channels for the members communication, community building and internationalisation activities • Access to major events, organised by the association or by other organisations in Europe and worldwide • Access to knowledge and initiatives on AI and Big Data from the European Commission and other key stakeholders • Possibility to use the association's channels to share knowledge about your projects, initiatives, achievements • Contribution to Task Forces leading to generation of AI and Big Data strategic knowledge and guidance at the EU level for policy makers and industry • Access to new business and research ideas and indication of possibilities to improve values to customers • Access to a network of experts in AI and Big Data • Access to privileged networks and key networking opportunities and matchmaking event organised by BDVA and others • Access to an R&I ecosystem of AI and Big Data players for consortium building, including technology and sectorial organisations • Early access to upcoming calls' information • through regular newsletters/access to in-depth information and presentations on the calls • Facilitation of contacts/links between business and industry for the establishment of common projects

Big Data Value association (BDVA)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to research and experimentation infrastructures
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	<p>The operational structure of the BDVA is organized in task forces that have as main aim provide a response to a specific activity within the objectives of the association. These are overseen by the Board of Directors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TF1 Programme: Provides inputs to the H2020 Programme content of the BDV PPP • TF2 Impact: Monitors the impact KPIs defined for the PPP • TF3 Community: Big data community engagement and participation • TF4 Communication: Communication activities to create awareness around the association (BDVA) • TF5 Policy and Societal: closing the gap between big data technologies and legal, societal and policy matters • TF6 Technical: identification of the technical challenges of the programme • TF7 Application: Group(s) that are domain-related and that can influence the other task forces. • TF8 Business: Business and economic influences and business areas such as Web Entrepreneurs and SMEs • TF9 Skills and Education: Skills needed for all aspects related to big data and artificial intelligence. <p>Under each Task force, several sub-groups, more focused also exist. The results of these sub-groups are position papers, whitepapers, memorandum of understanding, and so on.</p>
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	<p>BDVA members (more than 120) include large industries, SMEs, research organisations and data users and providers.</p> <p>The BDVA is composed of the following different types of memberships [21]:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Full members: they can participate in all activities of the association, have full voting rights in the General Assembly (see below), can be part of the Board of Directors (see below). 2. Associate members: they can participate in the activities of the association by they do not have any voting rights.
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	NA
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	NA
MEMBERSHIP FEES	Both types of membership have an annual membership fee [22] layered on the type of organisation (Large, SME, academia, other), and that of as 2020 are as follows:

Big Data Value association (BDVA)																
	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>Full Members</th> <th>Associate Members</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Large Industry</td> <td>9.500 €</td> <td>2.500 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Small or Medium Enterprise</td> <td>1.500 €</td> <td>500 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Academia / Research</td> <td>1.500 €</td> <td>500 €</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Others</td> <td>1.500 €</td> <td>500 €</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Full Members	Associate Members	Large Industry	9.500 €	2.500 €	Small or Medium Enterprise	1.500 €	500 €	Academia / Research	1.500 €	500 €	Others	1.500 €	500 €
	Full Members	Associate Members														
Large Industry	9.500 €	2.500 €														
Small or Medium Enterprise	1.500 €	500 €														
Academia / Research	1.500 €	500 €														
Others	1.500 €	500 €														
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	NA															
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANIZED PER YEAR	Webinars (several), Data Week (annual), BDVA Activity Groups meetings, BDVA General Assembly, European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)															
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	In growth															
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	The European Commission															

3.2.3 European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO)

European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO)	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	ECSO is an ASBL (not-for-profit association under the laws of Belgium)
DATE OF CREATION	June 2016
MISSION STATEMENT	The main goal of ECSO is to coordinate the development of the European Cybersecurity Ecosystem support the protection of European Digital Single Market, ultimately to contribute to the advancement of European digital sovereignty and strategic autonomy.
STRUCTURE	Governance structure of ECSO [23]

European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO)	
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	<p>All cybersecurity research topics, including especially sub-groups under the following topic headings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cybersecurity Ecosystem • Digital Transformation in Verticals • Data & Economy • Basic & Disruptive Technologies • Cybersecurity for Dual Use Technologies
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<p>Services provided to members are clustered around:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FEDERATE & CONNECT: ECSO Federates the European Cybersecurity Public and Private Community and facilitates the networking and cooperation at European level • ACT: ECSO Supports members' needs and market development in public-private cooperation with concrete actions/initiatives geared towards increasing strategic autonomy. • SUPPORT: ECSO is a recognised actor in the European institutional landscape, it cooperates with European institutions, bodies and agencies as well as National Public administrations for the development and implementation of EU policies, programmes and legislations to increase digital autonomy.
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECSO Working Group 1 (Standardisation, Certification and Supply Chain Management) • ECSO Working Group 2 (Market Deployment, Investments and International Collaboration) • ECSO Working Group 3 (Cyber Resilience of Economy, Infrastructure & Services) • ECSO Working Group 4 (Support to SMEs, Coordination with Countries and Regions) • ECSO Working Group 5 (Education, Training, Awareness, Cyber Ranges)

European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECSO Working Group 6 (SRIA and Cyber Security Technologies)
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 257 Members • 22 Public Administrations from EU Member States • 44 Large Companies • 58 SMEs • 29 Associations • 16 Users/Operators • 73 RTOs/Universities • 9 Regions/Clusters • 6 Investors
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	29 European Countries represented (EU Member States, Switzerland and Turkey)
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	Information not shared
MEMBERSHIP FEES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Public Administrations = €0 per year • Regions/Clusters = €2000 per year • Micro-SMEs = €1000 per year • Small SMEs = €2000 per year • Medium Size SMEs = €4000 per year • Large Companies = €12000 per year • Research Organisations = €1000 to €6000 per year depending upon size • Universities = €2000 per year • Associations = €1500 to €6000 per year depending upon budget size • Users = €1000 to €2000 per year depending upon size
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	Horizon 2020 projects
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 or 3 investor events • 1 or 2 high level events (C level, European Institutions) • 10-20 annual operational activities events (working group level)
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	Growth +2 or +3 new members per month
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission • ENISA • European Parliament • European Council • Other EU Institutions

3.2.4 European Organisation for Security (EOS)

[24](EOS)	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	EOS is a corporation under the laws of Belgium, run as a not-for-profit entity
DATE OF CREATION	June 2007
MISSION STATEMENT	The European Organisation for Security (EOS) [24] is the voice of the European security industry and research community. Operating in 15 different countries, EOS Members provide security research, solutions and services across many security domains, including border, cyber, transport and crisis management.
STRUCTURE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Assembly • Board of Directors • Task Forces • Working Groups <p>EOS' GOVERNANCE - All EOS Members are represented in the General Assembly which approves annual financial statements and appoints the Board of Directors. The Board of Directors is the governing body of EOS, which looks after EOS members' interests and is empowered to set EOS policy, objectives and overall direction.</p>
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	All cybersecurity research topics – under the EOS Cybersecurity Working Group
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<p>The complexity of European security threats calls for sophisticated and long-term solutions. As a result, the security industry is increasingly reliant on cooperation and consortia to bring innovation to market. EOS works closely with its Members and the broader industry and research community to form consortia that are successfully participating in major European research and innovation projects. In this way, the voice of the security industry is shaping the future development of security solutions and driving the delivery of new commercial products in the long term.</p> <p>Through EOS, members</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Contribute to the development of business opportunities through EU-funded programs 2. Promote research priorities at EU level 3. Participate in EU-funded R&D projects 4. Gain visibility and profit from engagement with leading European decision makers 5. Promote security-related standards and certification frameworks 6. Cooperate across EU borders and with international organisations

[24](EOS)	
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Establish industry intelligence and good practice through EOS Working Groups 8. Gain better understanding of end-users' needs
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EOS Artificial Intelligence Task Force • EOS Research and Innovation Working Group • EOS Border Security Working Group • EOS Soft Target and Critical Infrastructures Protection Working Group • EOS Security Screening and Detection Technologies Working Group (SSDWG) • EOS Cybersecurity Working Group
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	<p>36 Members</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GROUP 1: Large industries and RTOs (more than 250 employees) • GROUP 2: Sectorial, trade or business associations • GROUP 3: SMEs, mid-size RTOs / institutes and clusters (50 to 250 employees) • <u>GROUP 4</u>: micro-SMEs and universities (less than 50 employees)
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	15 European Countries represented (EU Member States, Switzerland and Turkey)
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	Information not shared
MEMBERSHIP FEES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large Companies = €14'520 per year • SMEs (small and medium) = €6'930 per year • Micro-SMEs = €3'465 per year • RTOs = €3'465 to €14'520 per year depending upon size
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	Horizon 2020 projects
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 or 2 high level events (C level, European Institutions) • 5-7 annual operational activities events (working group level)
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	Decline -2 to -3 members per year
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission • ENISA • European Parliament

[24](EOS)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Council • Other EU Institutions • National EU Member State Administrations • National Government Agencies • ECAC
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3.2.5 GAIA-X, European Association for Data and Cloud

GAIA-X, European Association for Data and Cloud	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	Association internationale sans but lucratif (AISBL)
DATE OF CREATION	2019 (September 2020 for the AISBL)
MISSION STATEMENT	<p>“As the impact of data-driven applications on the European economy has grown over the years, emerging digital ecosystems are faced with a variety of challenges that inhibit further development and collaboration. The project Gaia-X addresses them through the establishment of data and infrastructure ecosystems according to European values and standards. Gaia-X allows data to become more widely available, as it opens up high-value shared data spaces and datasets across the EU. It fosters the creation, formation, roll-out and growth of digital ecosystems that can be commercially leveraged in and across data spaces. Gaia-X drives value, business cases and innovation towards different target groups including consumers, providers and facilitators such as industry, the public sector or academia”. [25]</p>
STRUCTURE	<p>The GAIA-X AISBL is composed of 3 main bodies [26]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Board of Directors (BoD), which is elected by the General Assembly. Only organizations with worldwide headquarters in Europe can be elected to the Board. Board members are elected for 2-year terms. It is the decision-making body of the organization. • The Policy Rules Committee (PRC), which appointed by the Board of Directors. The PRC defines the Policy Rules Document which lays out rules to be fulfilled by members and services declared within GAIA-X to reflect the "European Values" of GAIA-X (Transparency, Data Protection, Portability, Security). • The Technical Committee (TC), which is chaired by the CTO, which defines the Architecture of Standards. • Data Spaces Business Committee <p>Furthermore, in addition to the AISBL there are other ways to participate in Gaia-X:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gaia-X Hubs: national grouping of companies, RTOs, associations, which is governed by a Representative Board, consisting of members of the Steering committee. Participants in the national hubs may or may not be members of the AISBL

GAIA-X, European Association for Data and Cloud	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gaia-X community: organized as work packages open to everyone, members or not of the AISBL. These open work packages work in collaboration with the Working groups of the AISBL.
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Domain-independent topics. Federated, decentralized cloud architectures; security and trustworthiness of cloud-based systems; open source; open interfaces Domain-specific topics. These are selected within the (currently) eight domain working groups (see section below)
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<p>Federation Services are offered to the institutional members. Technical implementation of these Federation Services focuses on the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the implementation of secure federated identity and trust mechanisms (security and privacy by design) sovereign data services which ensure the identity of source and receiver of data and which ensure the access and usage rights towards the data easy access to the available providers, nodes and services. Data provided through federated catalogues the integration of existing standards to ensure interoperability and portability across infrastructure, applications and data the establishment of a compliance framework and Certification and Accreditation services the contribution of a modular compilation of open source software and standards to support providers in delivering a secure, federated and interoperable infrastructure
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	Eight domain working groups for innovation: Industry 4.0/SME, Smart Living, Finance, Health, Public Sector, Mobility, Agriculture and Energy.
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	Institutional members only (not individual), consisting of companies and research organisations. 22 founding members. Currently under review are applications from over 300 institutional members.
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	Pan-European. Major founding members are Germany and France.
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	Not known.

GAIA-X, European Association for Data and Cloud															
MEMBERSHIP FEES	<p>5. The Standard Fee (SF) is:</p> <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Annual Revenue [EUR]</th> <th>Annual Fee [EUR]</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>> = 10bn</td> <td>75.000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>> = 1bn</td> <td>45.000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>> = 100m</td> <td>20.000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>> = 10m</td> <td>10.000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>< 10m</td> <td>5.000</td> </tr> <tr> <td>NPOs</td> <td>2.500</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Annual Revenue [EUR]	Annual Fee [EUR]	> = 10bn	75.000	> = 1bn	45.000	> = 100m	20.000	> = 10m	10.000	< 10m	5.000	NPOs	2.500
Annual Revenue [EUR]	Annual Fee [EUR]														
> = 10bn	75.000														
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> = 100m	20.000														
> = 10m	10.000														
< 10m	5.000														
NPOs	2.500														
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	Special emphasis on national funding programmes. The German BMWi has initiated several funding programs, that promote the use of artificial intelligence and smart data. The French government will support national projects for data sharing through its national strategy for artificial intelligence.														
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	During the pandemic, mostly virtual webinars. Following the Gaia-X Summit in November 2020, the association is currently organising various web seminars for its members and interested parties. The first event, organised by the Association’s Technical Committee, took place on February 17th, 2021. The committee offered insights into the latest progress of the work packages through a virtual Technical Deep Dive, and the community shared demos and ideas about Gaia-X’s technical development. These activities will continue through 2021 and be adjusted as the pandemic subsides.														
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	In growth.														
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	European Commission National hubs, which have a mandate by their national authorities														

3.2.6 Institution of Analysts and Programmers (IAP)

IAP – the Institution of Analysts and Programmers [27]	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	Incorporated as a company limited by guarantee and operates as a registered charity in England and Wales (Charity Number 1179558)
DATE OF CREATION	1972
MISSION STATEMENT	<p>Vision</p> <p>The vision for the Institution of Analysts and Programmers is to improve software for society by being the leading professional body for those aspiring to and engaged in creating, developing and maintaining software, with an international reputation for education, high standards and the calibre of its members.</p> <p>Mission</p> <p>The mission of the Institution of Analysts and Programmers is to be the leading specialist professional body advancing software development, recognising the competence of those engaged in all aspects of it, and promoting the importance of trustworthy software to the public.</p> <p>We need to ensure that our members adhere to the highest professional standards, are committed to their own development and abide by their duty to serve the public interest in their work.</p>
STRUCTURE	Governed by its Trustee Board comprising the President, the Deputy President, Director General, Operations Director (Non-Voting), Membership Director, Education Director and other elected members (3 years before re-election).

IAP – the Institution of Analysts and Programmers [27]	
	The Executive runs the organisation on a day-to-day basis and comprises the President, the Deputy President, Director General, Operations Director, Membership Director, Education Director.
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General software and software development. • Trustworthy Software Initiative • Trustworthy Software Foundation
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance – We will enhance what we offer to our members by focusing on career-oriented benefits that will help them develop professionally. • Exchange – We will provide our members with opportunities to exchange ideas, both face-to-face and online. • Encourage – We will actively encourage our members to develop their careers by finding them mentors from within our membership. • Empower – We will empower our members, especially our Fellows, to have a greater voice within our profession. • Ensure – We will ensure the quality of our membership remains outstanding by extending the peer review procedure that applications receive and by providing online verification of membership. • Enable – We will enable members to contribute more to the running and development of the Institution by establishing opportunities for them to help the Institution flourish. • Educate – We will continue to educate our members and the wider profession by publishing a learned journal and by developing a Body of Knowledge for the profession. • Enlighten – We will enlighten our profession, shaping its development by liaising more with government, academia and employers. • Engender – We will engender the spirit of professional duty in our members so that they can evangelise the need for professionalism in the wider IT community. • Evolve – We will evolve into a higher profile and more significant specialist professional body by increasing our relevance to our own members, the wider profession and Society at large.
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	None found?
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	Grades of membership: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student • Licentiate (LIAP) • Graduate Member (GRADIAP) • Associate Member (AMIAP) • Member (MIAP)

IAP – the Institution of Analysts and Programmers [27]	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fellow (FIAP) • Distinguished Fellow (DFIAP)
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	Not known
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	Not known
MEMBERSHIP FEES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licentiate (LIAP) - £75 • Graduate Member (GRADIAP) - £85 • Associate Member (AMIAP) - £105 • Member (MIAP) - £125 • Fellow (FIAP) - £150 • Distinguished Fellow (DFIAP) - £150
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events • Organisational membership though no details available
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	Symposium
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	Not known
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	UK academic institutions and companies

3.2.7 NEM Initiative (New European Media Initiative)

NEM Initiative (New European Media Initiative) [28]	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	European Technology Platform
DATE OF CREATION	2014
MISSION STATEMENT	NEM Initiative mission is to foster the impact of interactive technologies on the future of new media.
STRUCTURE	<p>The NEM governance is based on the following structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEM General Assembly consisting of all interested stakeholders – NEM members which are mainly public and private organisations. • NEM Steering Board – involving a representative set of players of all domains of the Networked and Electronic Media, defining the strategic vision and the key orientations of the Initiative, aiming at converting the NEM vision into a strategic agenda, and setting the operational goals for achieving this agenda

NEM Initiative (New European Media Initiative) [28]	
	NEM Executive Group – a subset of the Steering Board who, together with NEM Office, take the responsibility for the day-to-day management of the activities of the initiative and the handling of all working relationships.
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	<p>From the last SRIA [29]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future Media Formats: 5D Light Field Video, Volumetric Media • Smart Media Networks: 5G and Future Networks for content creation and distribution ATAWAD, including coding/decoding, Personal and Usage Data Management and Exploitation for Media, Network Based Media Services, Energy optimization for content creation, transmission, processing and storage, Cybersecurity • AI for Media and Content: Artificial Intelligence and Content, Artificial Intelligence and Hyper-Personalisation for Media Access Services <p>Future Media Applications and Challenges: New European converged and social media technologies for other vertical sectors, Social eXtended Reality, UX: Immersive and Interactive technologies for content and creation, Disinformation.</p>
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get in direct contact with main stakeholders from Media, Content, Creative industries, Social Media, Broadcasting, Telecom, Immersive technologies, and Consumer electronics sectors in Europe • Explore participation in EU and other publicly funded research and innovation programs and actions • Increases visibility of its members • Have the opportunity for early registration to any future Society professional and networking events • Are eligible to vote in Society decisions, such as electing trustees or changing the constitution • Are eligible to stand for election as a trustee • Are eligible to volunteer or be nominated for working groups or committees that the trustees may establish
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New digital media opportunities • Next generation Internet • Digital Innovation Hubs • G PPP Media pilot • NEM Vision / Strategy
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	1200 members

NEM Initiative (New European Media Initiative) [28]	
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	Mainly European
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS FOR THE ORGANISATION (IF KNOWN)	NA
MEMBERSHIP FEES	Membership is free and open to all
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	NA
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	Several events and workshops and summits per year.
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	Not known.
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	European Commission

3.2.8 NESSI-The Networked European Software and Services Initiative

NESSI-The Networked European Software and Services Initiative	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	European Technology Platform (ETP)
DATE OF CREATION	2006
MISSION STATEMENT	<p>As stated in the latest NESSI Manifesto [30] – the mission of NESSI is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide thought leadership in Europe on the convergence of the networks of data, things and services and the transformation into a new digital society, on the technological and socio-economic implications, and on the consequent business opportunities; • drive convergence and transformation by strengthening and advancing the software and service-based economies in Europe; and • stimulate the creation of ecosystems around software, services, and data; and • provide visionary, comprehensive input to the European Commission, thereby shaping the European research and innovation agenda.
STRUCTURE	Each ETP shall define its governance structure. In the case of NESSI it is as follows:

NESSI-The Networked European Software and Services Initiative	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NESSI Board: all members are part of the NESSI board and provide some financial support for the operations [31] • NESSI Steering Committee is the body responsible for the definition, implementation and monitoring of NESSI activities [32] <p>The membership is free and is open to every organization that is legally established, has a legal presence in Europe, is either an ICT SME, ICT Large organization, academia or are users, and provide a letter of intent sharing the vision and mission of NESSI.</p>
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	<p>From the last white paper [33]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced software development methods for electronic components and systems • Software-driven integration of KDT (Key Digital Technologies) applications • Trustworthiness of software and software development for KDT • Managing complexity, dynamics, and uncertainty of KDT applications • Software for Spatial Computing • Software for sustainability and energy efficiency
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to software and service technology challenges at the top of the European and national policy agendas • Access to key stakeholders • Tune internal research and innovation strategies with research programmes within Europe • Increase organisation's visibility on the national and EU research arena • Increase the networking and cooperation capacity of the members • Receive first-hand information from policy and programme makers and network with other key actors on the EU research arena
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software and Key Digital Technologies • Software and Smart Networks and Services • Open Source Software • Software and the Next Generation Internet • Software and AI
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	NESSI has over 450 Members, representing major stakeholders across the ICT domain, with a balance between large enterprises, SMEs, research institutes and academia.
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	European

NESSI-The Networked European Software and Services Initiative	
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	Not known.
MEMBERSHIP FEES	The membership is free and is open to every organization that is legally established, has a legal presence in Europe, is either an ICT SME, ICT Large organization, academia or are users, and provide a letter of intent sharing the vision and mission of NESSI [34].
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	NESSI seeks funding through the participation of the ETP in coordination and support actions, such as the NESSI 2010 Support Action [35].
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	Several a year.
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	Not known.
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	European Commission

3.2.9 Open Forum Europe (OFE)

Open Forum Europe (OFE) [36]	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	Not-for-profit (AISBL), Brussels-based independent think tank
DATE OF CREATION	2002
MISSION STATEMENT	The openness principles which guide all our activities are: user centricity, competition, flexibility, sustainability, and the importance of relying on the support of a transparent and open community.
STRUCTURE	Shallow hierarchy, with CEO, Chairman, Non-Executive Directors, Policy Advisors, and an independent global network of “OpenForum Academy Fellows”. Policy Research and Development team based in Brussels, and a chapter in the UK.
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	Open Source, Open standards, Digital Government, public procurement, Intellectual Property, cloud computing and Internet policy.
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	Frequent webinars and community discussion calls are sponsored, as well as regular initiatives on specific topics, such as the current state of open source in Europe (a study nearing completion by Fraunhofer ISI jointly with OFE).

Open Forum Europe (OFE) [36]	
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	No working groups as such – rather, initiatives that are organized according to certain topics. An example is a Blockchain Observatory.
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	OFE prefers to speak in terms of “supporters” and “partners”. The partners tend to be institutional – for example, the Free Software Foundation Europe, the Eclipse Foundation, GitHub, IBM, Oracle, and Red Hat. In contrast, “supporters” are individuals generally, who need not have any particular affiliation.
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	Mostly continental Europe and the UK, with significant participation from the USA in terms of “Academy Fellows” and institutional partners. Some participation from Oceania.
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	Unknown.
MEMBERSHIP FEES	Appear to be none.
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	Unclear whether the support received from institutional partners also involves financial support.
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	Webinars, conferences, community meetings.
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	Appears to be growing.
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	OFE works closely with the European Commission, the European Parliament, national and local governments, both directly and via its national partners.

3.2.10 RSE-The Society of Research Software Engineers

RSE-The Society of Research Software Engineers [37]	
FORM OF THE ORGANISATION	Charitable incorporated organisation
DATE OF CREATION	March 2019
MISSION STATEMENT	The mission of RSE is to establish a research environment that recognises the vital role of software in research. We work to increase software skills across everyone in research, to promote collaboration between researchers and software experts, and to support the creation of an academic career path for Research Software Engineers.
STRUCTURE	Board of Trustees elected directly by the membership for two-year terms (12 members including: president, vice-president, treasurer,

RSE-The Society of Research Software Engineers [37]	
	<p>vice-treasurer secretary and leads for several aspects: Web, infrastructure, conference, etc.).</p> <p>The current board was elected in October 2019. Half of the trustees were elected from amongst the founding trustees and half were newly elected. Just under half of those eligible cast a vote: 109 of the 228 members.</p>
LANDSCAPE OF RESEARCH TOPICS ADDRESSED	Not really research topics. Networking, interesting materials, training information, careers information etc.
SERVICES PROVIDED TO MEMBERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the work of the Society to further research software engineering • Are eligible to apply for any future opportunities for Society funding • Have the opportunity for early registration to the Society annual conference • Have the opportunity for early registration to any future Society professional and networking events • Are eligible to vote in Society decisions, such as electing trustees or changing the constitution • Are eligible to stand for election as a trustee • Are eligible to volunteer or be nominated for working groups or committees that the trustees may establish
WORKING GROUPS IN THE ORGANISATION	Working groups per region (30 in UK) and some abroad.
NUMBER AND TYPE OF MEMBERS	228 members (individuals)
GEOGRAPHIC COVERAGE OF MEMBERS	<p>Mainly UK but also international RSE Associations in</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Australia/New Zealand • Belgium • Germany • Netherlands • Nordic • USA
TOTAL REVENUE AND COSTS (IF KNOWN)	NA
MEMBERSHIP FEES	20 pounds (annual fee).
OTHER REVENUE / INCOME SOURCES	NA
TYPE OF EVENTS ORGANISED PER YEAR	1 conference.

RSE-The Society of Research Software Engineers [37]	
MEMBERSHIP IN GROWTH OR IN DECLINE (IF KNOWN)	In growth
PRIMARY INTERLOCUTORS	Academic institutions and UK government.

4 Questionnaires and Interviews

In order to perform a landscape analysis to identify gaps and opportunities for cross-fertilisation and growth in the European software technologies, digital infrastructure, and cybersecurity sectors, SWForum.eu launched a survey aimed at academia, industry, and public administrations involved in the fields of software technologies, digital infrastructure, and cybersecurity.

4.1 Questionnaires

The intent of the questionnaire was to get a snapshot picture using a broad set of questions which are then essentially custom fitted for each potential category of stakeholders. The initial categories include, but are not limited to: Research, Academic (universities / colleges), SMEs, Industry, and Government (public sector). The idea was to keep the questionnaire as short and to the point as possible, so that the greatest number of respondents would contribute input and thus presenting an opportunity to better understand the concerned and relevant stakeholders.

4.1.1 Questionnaire Target Audience

The questionnaires were customized for each target audience in order to make it more focused and concise. The objective of the questionnaires was to collect input from different stakeholders of relevance to SwForum.eu, making it multi source. With this in mind, we categorized the audience in the following groups:

- Industry
- SMEs
- Academia and research institutes (universities/colleges)
- Public Administrations (governments)

For each of the groups, specific questions were created and are provided in detail in the next section. It should be noted that the questionnaires were answered on behalf of each individual. We have targeted individuals working for different types or organizations or institutions.

4.1.2 Questionnaire Content and Reasoning

In this sub-section, the questions posed for each of the target groups are explained. The questions are included as annexes and they can be accessed in the EU Survey link <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/SWForumSurvey2021>.

The questions were categorized under the following groups:

- **Profiling:** This set of questions was used for the profiling of the respondents. Based on the answers to these questions, the background of the respondents was identified, and only relevant questions were made to each of the groups. Here the origin country, the type of organisation and even the focus of the organization were identified.
- **Questionnaire for the private sector (Industrial +SMEs):** The questions for the industry, including SMEs and big industries were included under this category. Here, questions related to the following topics were included:
 - Generic questions about their type of business
 - Questions related to the usage/creation of OS and participation in OS communities
 - Questions related to trustworthiness software
 - Questions related to software standards
 - Questions related to clusters or organizations the companies belong to

 Questionnaire for Academia: In this category, questionnaires targeted to academic institutions and research institutes were included, as follows:

- Generic questions about their areas of research
- Questions about research topics, their relevance and evolution
- Questions related to relevance of OS and development of OS assets in research projects
- Questions related to compliance issues

 Questionnaires for public administrations: This set of questions included:

- Generic question about the level of PA (local, regional, national)
- Questions about the policies on the use of OS
- Questions about digital transformation and infrastructures
- Questions about the existence of procurement's plans, including certifications and methodologies
- Questions about disruptive technologies used in the PAs

All these questions were specifically designed to gather the audience's opinion on the main three pillars of SWForum.eu, i.e., digital infrastructures, software development and cybersecurity. At the same time, other relevant aspects such as the future research topics in the software domain, standardisation, open source or software clusters are associations which were included in the questionnaires with the objective of feeding other needs and studies that we are performing in SWForum.eu.

4.1.3 Questionnaire Responses and Analysis

The questionnaire was distributed extensively through consortium partners' contacts, LinkedIn, ongoing projects and webinars. It should be noted that in the current environment of the pandemic, there has been an overload of surveys, webinars and zoom interactions which has led to some fatigue. However, despite this challenge a total of 57 replies were received, as follows:

Table 9: Questionnaire analysis -European-based replies according to type of audience

European-based replies according to Audience	Number of replies
Academic institutions	16
Research institutes	16
SMEs	13
Private sector industrial	9
Public	3
Total	57

Of the above, outside Europe, 9 replies were from:

Table 10: Questionnaire analysis - Non-European-based replies according to type of audience

Replies outside of Europe according to Audience	Number of replies
Academic institutions	3
Research institutes	2
SMEs	3
Private sector	1
Total	9

From the 48 replies within Europe and 9 replies from outside Europe, the geographical distribution is displayed in Figure 4-1:

Figure 4-1: Questionnaire analysis - Geographical indication of all replies

4.1.3.1 Focus of the organizations

In response to the question requesting the focus of each organization, the following responses were received:

- 📦 Of the SMEs, 11 were **service driven** whereas 2 were **industrial driven** with one SME focused on **AI**;
- 📦 Of the Public Administrations, 1 was focused on **AI**;
- 📦 Of the Research Institutes, the distribution was, as follows:
 - 2 multidisciplinary
 - 2 R&D, Innovation projects, lab services
 - 2 on logistic and industry
 - 1 high-performance architecture – big data
 - 1 on some kind of research
 - 1 on a variety of technologies in various domains

- 1 ICT

4.1.3.2 Primary product or service of your organization:

In response to the question on the primary product or service of the organization, 22 replies were received, specifically, 13 SMEs and 9 private sector organizations provided information on their primary line of business, as follows:

Table 11: Questionnaire analysis -Primary product or service

Type of primary product or service	Number of organizations
Services	18
Software / Firmware	9
Product(s) (including components, systems, etc)	7
System(s) integration	6

More specifically, for 7 of the above replies, this detailed into provision of the following services and/or products:

- ▣ 6 companies working in consulting,
- ▣ 1 in ICT consulting

with a further level of detail given on the types of service, as follows:

- ▣ SaaS Cloud Solution for Document & Workflow Management
- ▣ Telco infrastructure
- ▣ Port Solution Suite
- ▣ IoT, edge and cloud products
- ▣ Software/System integration in several vertical sectors: Health, Finance, Telecommunications, Logistics, Aerospace, etc
- ▣ Open source software support Networking and value-added services for the research and education community in Europe
- ▣ Data curation
- ▣ Quality control device
- ▣ Systems integration
- ▣ CMS
- ▣ ICT Services

4.1.3.3 Software Development

A number of questions related to software development were presented and the two types of audience which responded were SMEs and the private sector.

Question: Do you develop or sell software with your offering? And if so, how is this done?

- ▣ Of the 13 replies from SMEs, 7 replied that they develop or sell software with their offering, 6 SMEs had their own inhouse team

- Of the 9 replies from the private sector, 7 replied that they develop or sell software with their offering, 6 companies had their own inhouse team.

Table 12: Questionnaire analysis - Software development teams

Audience	Inhouse team	Outsourcing in Europe	Outsourcing in US	Outsourcing in Asia	Buy third party software
SME	6	2	1		1
Private sector	6	2		2	

The sectors covered by SMEs were:

- Maritime
- Smart agriculture and cities
- Research and education
- Health and care
- Business and government agencies
- Logistics
- Government, medical and maritime

The sectors covered by the private sector were:

- B2B and eGovernment
- Teleconference services
- Manufacturing
- Airlines
- Web

Concerning the development and/or use of proprietary and/or opensource software, 14 replies (from SMEs and the private sector) were received, as follows:

- 5 develop and/or use proprietary software,
- 3 develop and/or use opensource software,
- 6 develop and/or use proprietary software as well as develop and/or use opensource software.

The type of software developed and/or used by both SMEs and private sector were described as: Tools, office, infrastructure, web.

The type of methodology used for software development by SMEs and the private sector were: Agile, Agile/DevOps, Waterfall; iterative, Scrum.

4.1.3.4 Concerns about software development

Question: Does your organisation belong to any associations or clusters which support your organisation's greatest concerns and which issues are addressed (multiple responses)?

To the above question on concerns, there were 22 replies (from SMEs and the private sector):

- 11 affirmative replies
- 11 negative replies

Table 13: Questionnaire analysis - Concerns about software development

Type of cluster	Number of replies received
New projects and innovation funding	9
Partnering opportunities	5
Industrial lobbying	5
Tender and call for proposal monitoring	4
Other	2

The supporting associations mentioned were:

- AEI Ciberseguridad
- ARTEMIS
- Bitkom
- EOS
- ECSO
- ETSI
- Gaia-X
- Géant
- H2020 SME Europe NGI
- IT-Cluster Austria
- IoT Forum
- SME Digital Alliance
- Trust-in-Digital Life
- VDI

Question: Is your company (developers) part of any OS community?

To the above question on concerns, there were 18 replies (from SMEs and the private sector):

- 7 affirmative replies
- 11 negative replies

The following OS communities to which the audience belonged were mentioned, as follows:

- INSPIRE
- OGC
- OW2
- Drupal

Question: Is your company promoting the participation of the company developers in open source community (i.e. extra incentives)?

To the above question on concerns, there were 7 replies (from SMEs and the private sector):

- 5 affirmative replies
- 2 negative replies

The dominance of affirmative replies is in line with the results of the European Commission Open Source Study carried out jointly by Fraunhofer ISI and OpenForum Europe in 2020-2021 [38]. In this study, a trend was noted toward investments by companies in their employees participating directly in open source development (i.e. on salary of the company, rather than voluntarily in their free time) [39].

This clearly reflects a growing awareness of the centrality of open source in software development in general. In the First SWForum.eu Workshop on Trustworthy Software and Open Source in March 2021, Keynote Tony Wasserman cited an annual study of Synopsys of proprietary applications (1250 audited applications in 17 industries), in which an astonishing 99% of analyzed codebases contained open source software.

SMEs are particularly active in both the use of and contributions to open source software. In the Commission study, it was revealed that more than 75% of the most active companies participating in OSS are SMEs.

The main concerns about using third party software are given in Figure 4-2 below:

Figure 4-2: Questionnaire analysis - Third party Open Source Software concerns

Security has clearly become the dominant factor in reluctance to include open source in deployed applications and products. The Commission has acknowledged this problem in its Open Source Strategy 2020 – 2023 document [40]. One of the main governing principles put forth in that document is continuous security testing of open source code bases to instill confidence in their security. This is an expensive proposition for an SME, who must generally rely on the community for this.

Quality and maintenance are the two other major concerns regarding OSS. SMEs base much of their delivered software on open source, because of the fast time to market but lack of maintenance (e.g. updates of modules amid major codebase upgrades) and quality (e.g. buggy performance) can quickly sap time and effort, reducing the economic attractiveness of utilizing open source in products.

Interestingly, documentation of open source, while a problem, is nowhere near as critical as the other factors for SMEs: they are used to working with codebases and, while documentation is appreciated, it is not generally on the critical path for successful usage of open source.

Question: What are your organisation's greatest current concerns about software development and operation?

Figure 4-3: Questionnaire analysis - Main Concerns about Software Development and Operation

The main characteristics of trustworthy software for an organization, from a selection of “Reliable”, “Stable”, “Frequently Updated” and “Others” were expressed in the Figure below:

Figure 4-4: Questionnaire analysis - Characteristics of trustworthy software

“Others” mention “willingness of developers to listen to feedback and/or accept patches; not sharing data with other third parties”

Question: Are you organizationally accredited with e.g. standards?

In total, 19 replies were received (from SMEs and the private sector), as follows:

- 10 affirmative replies
- 9 negative replies

The standards mentioned were:

- ISO/IEC 27000 (8 replies)
- ISO 9000 (8 replies)
- BSI C5, SOC2, Wai-Aria, some others

Recommendations for SMEs and Private Industrial Actors concerning Open Source

- Actively encourage your employees not only to use open source software, but to contribute to open source communities that are strategic to your business area (e.g. the Drupal community for web development SMEs). Allow / encourage the employees to do this during work hours.
- Contribute actively to security-related initiatives in the open source communities. This may take several forms: if the company possess the appropriate skills, then active scanning and patching of vulnerabilities; otherwise, helping to report, share, and disseminate information about discovered vulnerabilities so that the community is kept regularly updated and an atmosphere of trust is created.

- ❏ Join Europe-wide initiatives for open source awareness-raising, such as OpenForum Europe. Lobby your governments for policies favouring the use of open source, e.g., in their procurement initiatives.

4.1.3.5 *Open source Software*

Question: Do you believe that open source software is as important as proprietary software?

In total, 32 replies were received from Research and Academic institutions, as follows:

- ❏ 30 affirmative replies
 - 15 Research institutions
 - 15 Academic
- ❏ 2 negative replies
 - 1 Research institution
 - 1 Academic

Once again, the overwhelming affirmative response reaffirms the general impression that open source has become an essential ingredient in the European software landscape.

The replies supporting Opensource software are reproduced hereafter:

- ❏ “It helps to make better apps and products, reduces learning curve, creates community of research
- ❏ It is a good way to learn how to do things and a useful source of tools
- ❏ Because it helps to improve the technologies [that] we all need to evolve in an equitable way.
- ❏ for sharing knowledge and make it more accessible
- ❏ avoid redundancy, agility, collaboration
- ❏ Not everybody can pay for proprietary software or can develop some things from scratch. Also, most times open source software is continuously updated and improved...
- ❏ They are important
- ❏ Because of the vast amount of mature technologies
- ❏ It promotes software security, software reuse, research
- ❏ Freedom
- ❏ Because the knowledge is open.
- ❏ Many public and private advancements rely on open source software (e.g. CERN, etc.)
- ❏ Because it is universal and included in almost all newly developed proprietary software
- ❏ trustability – robustness
- ❏ Open Source is extremely important for Europe as it will underpin future sustainability and ecosystems.
- ❏ Transparency, fair treatment of users
- ❏ It is now pervasive, and it has changed the way we develop, maintain, evolve, market, sell, etc. software.
- ❏ Open source facilitates the development of new software - no need to reinvent multiple wheels
- ❏ It is constantly reviewed, thus serious bugs and vulnerabilities are often quickly identified.
- ❏ Everyone can use it and enhance it.

- ❑ Even though still hard, open-source software can be audited by the community; the community is able to contribute, extend, and customize open-source software more easily; transparency is important for digital sovereignty and less dependency of a few major (often US based) companies;
- ❑ To allow the community to work together
- ❑ Open software facilitates security assessments
- ❑ No lock-in, better security, easier integration
- ❑ transparency of the code, facilitate synergies and collaboration
- ❑ Well supported open source projects can be even higher quality than proprietary ones”

The replies from the survey respondents match well to the results of the Commission-sponsored Fraunhofer/OpenForum Europe study [38] [39]. In order of precedence, the top-named incentives to joining open source development were the following:

- ❑ Finding technical solutions
- ❑ Knowledge seeking
- ❑ Avoiding vendor lock-in
- ❑ Carrying forward the state of the art of technology

In that same study, the top named realized benefits of open source were:

- ❑ Open standards and interoperability
- ❑ Independence from proprietary providers
- ❑ Improved source code access
- ❑ Active community for knowledge exchange

In both cases, the two surveys confirmed the key issues. SMEs in particular need independence from proprietary providers, because they generally cannot afford the extremely high prices involved (in some mission-critical domains, the costs of proprietary software products can run into the hundreds of thousands of Euros). SMEs also find particularly important the possibility to participate in communities in order to exchange knowledge and learn new technologies and systems, since they rarely have internal resources available for training and knowledge acquisition.

Question: Do you have ongoing open source software research projects?

To the above question, there were 32 replies (from Research and Academic institutions), as follows:

- ❑ 19 affirmative replies
- ❑ 13 negative replies

The open source software research projects mentioned were:

- ❑ ALIADA tool: <https://github.com/ALIADA/aliada-tool>
- ❑ Urbanite: <https://www.urbanite-project.eu/>
- ❑ PIACERE: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/solution>
- ❑ GNOME: <https://www.gnome.org/>
- ❑ FreeDesktop: <https://www.freedesktop.org/>
- ❑ OSSpal: <https://www.ossPAL.org/>
- ❑ FLOSSbok: <https://flossbok.org/>
- ❑ DECENTER: <https://www.decenter-project.eu/>

- 📦 ONTOCHAIN : <https://ontochain.ngi.eu/>
- 📦 Resilience modeling of OSS projects, no website, open source project list: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Open-Source-Analysis>
- 📦 Software Heritage: <https://www.softwareheritage.org>
- 📦 Cyber Sandbox Creator - <https://gitlab.ics.muni.cz/muni-kypo-csc/cyber-sandbox-creator>
- 📦 Trust Monitor (no web site, it's a GIT repository)
- 📦 H2020 projects

4.1.3.6 Research Agenda

Question: In which domains do you expect to see the most research interest going forward?

The response from the Academic/Research domain was significant when considering the overall response rate for the survey. Since it was possible to exclusively choose either academic or research organisations then from now on they are treated as the same in the following analysis since academic institutions for the most part are research organisations and in the following answers it is not possible to separate.

In total, 28 replies were received, as follows:

- 📦 Replies from 14 Academic Institutions
- 📦 Replies from 14 Research institutes

The desired topics of research covered:

- 📦 Artificial intelligence, and AI combined with big data, context aware systems, intelligent systems and distributed computing
- 📦 Cybersecurity, security, security of “runtime issues”, security and privacy by design, cybersecurity for emerging technologies
- 📦 Data Analytics, Big data, Data governance, data sharing
- 📦 Robotics
- 📦 Logistics, blockchain, “ontochain” type of technologies
- 📦 Smart cities
- 📦 Industrial, energy and health
- 📦 Bioengineering
- 📦 Software engineering, Computer game software, IoT software engineering, software process mining,
- 📦 Reproducibility,
- 📦 Space/Defence
- 📦 Digital sovereignty, quantum computing and its integration with traditional computing
- 📦 Quantum computing
- 📦 Security, formal methods of security,
- 📦 New interaction technologies to empower users and increase the bandwidth of communication between operators/users and computing devices

It is clear from the topics covered that many organisations are working in multiple different areas, likely a mix of end user domains and fundamental computer science areas. Further analysis/questioning of responders could establish a stronger link. Overall, though, of the domains/areas identified far more are applications, i.e. the organisations use software to solve problems in specific areas than do research in software itself, than specific research topics of software engineering.

Question: What is currently missing in most software engineering / technologies research agendas?

In total, 32 replies were received, as follows:

- 📄 Replies from 16 Academic Institutions
- 📄 Replies from 16 Research institutes

When considering what is missing from research agendas then it is important to understand the context of the respondent and therefore this connects with the responses to the previous question in this area. It should be noted that the method of distribution of the survey which emphasised channels connected with groups in the cybersecurity area and therefore may be a biased sample. Overall, though, the responses tend to highlight questions around the professionalization of software production and therefore are not really research agenda items but that should be valid areas which should not be blockers to receiving funding if they are highlighted.

Figure 4-5: Questionnaire analysis - Missing fields in software engineering/technologies research agendas

More than the 50% (38) of the answers were from academic (28%) and research institutions (28%).

- 📄 Open source:
 - Almost all the respondents (35) considered that opens source is as important as proprietary software. The reasons given for this were related to 1) the OS as an enabler for innovation (and open innovation) as research requires an active collaboration between stakeholders whose main interest must be the advancement of science creating communities of research, 2) avoids vendor lock-in and democratizes access to technological advances in an equitable way thus increasing business models which are available to small businesses 3) is more trustable and more secure as open source software can be inspected by the potential users and it is continuously updated and improved, increasing trust ability and robustness because serious bugs and vulnerabilities are often quickly identified.
 - 22 of them have ongoing OS projects, mainly European research projects.
- 📄 Research trends: When asked about the research topics going forward in the next years several of them were mentioned:

Cybersecurity
Applications
new software lifecycles for the computing continuum
new software design approaches for quantum computing
smart cities
Data Analytics
Automotive software
Context-aware systems
Artificial Intelligence
Robotics
Logistic
Energy
Health
Bioengineering
Computer game sw engineering
IOT
Software process mining
Reproducibility
Space
Defense
New interaction technologies to empower users and increa
Distributed computing

Figure 4-6: Listing of Future Research Topics

From these, cybersecurity and related topics (security "runtime issues", Blockchain, Ontochain type of technologies, Security and Privacy by design, formal methods for security and digital sovereignty) were the most cited research topic. The next one was artificial intelligence, followed by data analytics (including big data) and quantum computing.

Figure 4-7: Questionnaire analysis - Research Trends in demand

- Other missing research trends were mainly related with SDLC and cybersecurity:
 - The adoption of rigorous formal methods
 - Integration of ML/AI techniques in development, modern software development processes

- Blockchain at large
- Reproducibility, traceability, Big Code
- Formal methods

Compliance issues: The following chart represents the main areas in which compliance issues are challenging to address. The most significant response to the question of compliance issues is a technical one and it is unclear if this answer is 'there must be validation that there are no back doors or vulnerabilities to fulfil compliance requirements' or just a general requirement? Interestingly the second answer is 'cybersecurity' which is the domain as a total so there is significant uncertainty in the resolution of the answer.

Figure 4-8: Questionnaire analysis - Compliance Issues Most Difficult to Address

- ❏ Others mentioned: AI, cross-border data management compliance, Compliance to usability standards (see the issues with un-usable security mechanisms)
- ❏ Interests in compliance issues from the research perspective:
 - Quality in evolving software
 - Security by design
 - Cross regulatory issues, standards
 - Data governance
 - Incorporating AI in the software engineering process in the Fog
 - Everything related to cybersecurity, certification/qualification frameworks are weak
 - Cybersecurity with formal methods
 - Liability

In terms of compliance issues of interest there is a spread from highly technical areas and social science. Some are very specific and others incredibly general so follow up to gain further details would be useful.

4.2 Interviews

In order to gather deeper information about some of the targeted topics personal interviews have been planned with experts on specific matters. The first set of these interviews will start in June 2021 and will be done until the end of the year. Considering this calendar, the outcomes from these interviews will be reported in the second version of this deliverable D3.2 due in M27. Some of these interviews will be considered for publication through the SwForum.eu social networks under the agreement and consent from the interviewees.

In the following sections preliminary candidates for the list of interviewees are detailed as well as the first version of the interview script.

4.2.1 Interview Target Audience

In the following table the selected experts are categorized. Due to the public nature only generic data from these experts is shown, so that they cannot be identified, to comply with the GDPR.

Table 14: Initial list of experts for the interviews.

Expert	Background	Topic
Expert 1	Academia	Cybersecurity
Expert 2	Academia	Cybersecurity
Expert 3	Academia	SW Engineering
Expert 4	Academia	SW Engineering
Expert 5	Academia	Digital Infrastructures
Expert 6	Academia	Digital Infrastructures
Expert 7	Academia	Data Engineering
Expert 8	Academia	Artificial Intelligence
Expert 9	Industrial	Cybersecurity /SW Engineering
Expert 10	Industrial	Cybersecurity /Standardisation
Expert 11	Industrial	Digital Infrastructures
Expert 12	Industrial	Digital Infrastructures
Expert 13	Industrial	Open source
Expert 14	Industrial	Data Engineering
Expert 15	Public Administration	Digital Infrastructures
Expert 16	Public Administration	Digital Infrastructures /SW Engineering

From this initial list, the experts will be selected. Others will be added as the interviews move on depending on the expertise coverage achieved and the availability of the interviewees.

4.2.2 Interview script

The purpose of the interviews is to gather information from stakeholders involved in relevant topics for SwForum.eu such as the ones mentioned before. These interviews will be done in collaboration with the CSA Hub4Cloud as both CSAs are complementary in terms of topics. The experts will be approached once and information useful for both CSAs will be gathered. In this section, only the contents related to SWForum.eu are detailed.

The interview will be limited to a maximum of **20 minutes**. With the consent of the interviewees, it will be recorded using tools like Zoom or similar. The interview might be edited to just change cosmetics, but its content will not be altered. The result will be shared with

the interviewees before being published and it will be used as input to be included in the different analysis to be done in WP2, WP3 and WP4.

Interviews will start with the interviewees free time slot (up to 5 minutes) where they introduce their company/institution to be followed by their opinions on some of the following topics: Open Source, cybersecurity, software engineering, digital infrastructures.

4.2.3 Interview Topics

The preliminary description of the topics together with some examples of questions that could be asked during the interview is given hereafter. The script will be shared beforehand with the potential interviewees. They will have the freedom to decide on which topics they feel more comfortable with and they can select the questions they would like to answer. This first version of the interview will be enlarged and updated continuously.

4.2.3.1 Open Source

Open source is a business model widely extended for software solutions. We would like to know your vision on OS usage and development.

4.2.3.2 Cybersecurity

Security ensures the proper behaviour of infrastructures and applications against external attacks or internal risks. Critical areas within Security are cybersecurity analytics, privacy, risk analysis, compliance, cybersecurity metrics, workforce education or penetration testing.

4.2.3.3 Software Engineering and digital infrastructures

The significance of software has recently grown to the point of merging the role of software developers with that of infrastructure operators, of which main focus is the automation of infrastructure-related activities through the use of software, giving birth to the Infrastructure as Code trend, the engine of the DevOps movement. DevOps is an organizational change that consists of using software engineering tactics that reduce the technical and organizational distance between development and operation, leading to the creation of a single, well-coordinated team of people. Software Engineering trends are needed for the application developers and operators to embrace IaC for the Cloud Continuum from the DevOps perspective: i.e. FaaS, Osmotic computing, Serverless, etc.

4.2.4 Reference Questions that can be used during the Interviews

4.2.4.1 Cybersecurity:

- ❑ What are the characteristics of trustworthy software/infrastructure for your organization? i.e. Reliable, stable, frequently updated, secure.
- ❑ In your opinion, which compliance issues are most difficult to address? i.e. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), No "back doors" / vulnerabilities, Cybersecurity, Quality metrics, etc.

4.2.4.2 *Digital infrastructures:*

- ❑ What is the main reason to the gap between Digital infrastructures in general and Cloud Computing in USA/ASIA and EUROPE?
- ❑ In which areas should Europe invest in to accelerate its (cloud) deployment and compare with alternatives currently available in other regions?
- ❑ As a European user, what do you miss from current Digital infrastructures and CC offerings?
- ❑ If CC from other regions become unavailable. How far is Europe to have a CC that will offer at least the same level of performance and security?
- ❑ Despite the conspicuous benefits to customer's trustworthiness in cloud services, which result from leveraging recognized security certifications (just as evidenced by the EU Cybersecurity Act (EU CSA)), it is also true that European cloud providers currently face multiple challenges to certify their services specially related with the big fragmentation in the domain of existing certification schemes. What do you think in this respect? Do you know EUCS?

4.2.4.3 *SW engineering*

- ❑ Do you develop or sell software with your offering?
- ❑ If so, how is this done? In-house team, outsourcing in the EU, outsourcing in Europe, outsourcing in Asia, Outsourcing in North America, outsourcing elsewhere, directly Buy someone else's software.
- ❑ Do you use a methodology for software development and operation? Waterfall, Iterative, Agile, DevOps, Others.
- ❑ What are your organisation's greatest current concerns about software development and operation? Where are your main challenges? i.e. Automation of the processes, Skills, Financial viability, Regulatory issues, Bad tool support, etc.

4.2.4.4 *Open source*

- ❑ What is your experience/opinion on OS? Do you think it is as relevant as proprietary software? Why?

4.2.4.5 *Other*

Do you participate in any OS community? Which one?

5 Conclusions / Recommendations

5.1 Conclusions / Recommendations – Key Membership-Based Support Organisational Structure Aspects

In general, when looking at the most successful existing membership-based support organizational structures, the important key features always included:

- 1) **Clear statements of Mission and Objectives** for the Organisation on behalf of its members
- 2) **Services specifically designed and operating** for the benefit of the members (e.g. structured around key issues for the stakeholders)
- 3) **Governance structures** which include the members in all decision-making processes and enable and allow members to take leadership roles (e.g. Board of Directors, Working Groups, Task Forces, etc.)
- 4) **Advocacy and related support** for the benefit of the members toward the public sector, the private sector and even citizens and society (lobbying, regulatory recommendations, legislative recommendations, white papers, position papers, etc.)
- 5) **A fair fee structure for sustainability** with different levels of fees based upon the services provided and used and the ability of each of the membership categories to pay (e.g. lower fees for SMEs)
- 6) **Education elements** for the benefit of the membership and stakeholders
- 7) **Outreach and Dissemination of results** and advocacy to the larger ecosystem and circle of interested stakeholders (who for one reason or another may not be members)
- 8) **Networking opportunities** for joint projects and collaboration in research and development as well as commercial aspects
- 9) **Evolution of the membership-based support** organizational structure to adapt and adjust to the changing environment, changing ecosystem and the changing community (without this the organisation can quickly become obsolete)

And thus, due to the successful examples utilized, these Conclusions also fully represent the Recommendations for SWForum to follow in the establishment of all the organizational and structural requirements.

5.2 Categories of stakeholders

We have categories of stakeholders like Research Institutes (Banking/ Finance and other kind of research) and Private sector (industrial) and SME with focus on Software, AI, HP architectures, or are multidisciplinary.

SWForum is designed to cater mainly to the software development community and the stakeholders can thus be divided into these categories as shown next. While this is not the only way to divide them, they are relevant for the scope of SwForum:

- 1) Academic/Universities (with research included)
- 2) Research Organisations (not a university or academic) – RTO
- 3) Private Sector Large Companies
- 4) Private Sector SMEs
- 5) Public Sector (may be both developing software and using software as a stakeholder)

5.2.1 Academic / Universities specific conclusions / requirements

To form general conclusions for a specific domain from the small number of responses and current questions is difficult due to the breadth of responses in terms of what the academic research into software is being used for since the majority of software research in an academic organisation is now being used to provide outputs for a particular domain area with a small amount being fundamental research on software engineering itself.

It is clear that there are of course missing domains or areas. These are primarily aligned with the specific academic research interests of those that completed the survey. SwForum consortium would surmise though that for many the areas highlighted though are fairly common with research organisations and even those in the commercial domain who are also utilising software and software engineering for supporting end user areas.

We are seeing generally overall the importance of open source. This in many domains is becoming more and more accepted, whereas previously for fail safe type applications open source was less acceptable that is becoming less and less the case. This opens out the utilisation of research software into areas or domains for which it was not intended or beyond its current maturity level. There are many instances of this in the past and the increasing prevalence of open products and services will mean that there must be greater care taken in the suitability of outputs for their eventual end use case in future.

5.2.2 Research Organisations (RTOs) specific conclusions / requirements

Research institutes are focusing in particular on R&D and innovation projects, laboratory services, technology transfer, logistics and industry, variety of technologies, multi-sectorial.

The requirements for this group are related to networking activities and outreach their activities, as well as to be able to impact relevant initiatives such as the possibility to influence research agendas. RTOs need the networking activities to reach relevant stakeholders to whom they provide their services and research capabilities. At the same time and in order to re-direct and adapt their research strategies, they need to

- 1) be aware / participate in the design of the research agendas so that they can drive the research strategies based on their experience/ needs
- 2) look for potential collaboration and funding options. Supporting means to foster discussion on relevant research topics in order to gather the needs and contributions from the different communities is another of the primary requirements from the RTOs.

Due to the nature of this group of stakeholders whose primary mission is to translate the research techniques and goals from the research projects to the industry, specific collaboration and outreach with industry (especially early adopters of the technologies) is required.

5.2.3 Private Sector Large Companies specific conclusions / requirements

The questionnaires revealed that, not only do large private industrial companies deal extensively with software, but unlike in previous decades, have firmly transitioned from procurement with regard to software to the establishment of in-house software development teams. The more mission-critical the particular domain in which the company is involved (e.g. transport, ranging from airlines to rail to automotive), the more the developed software is specific to the products of that company, and the more it is protected by IPR measures related to competitive strategy. As noted in Section 5.2.1, this has partly to do with a reluctance to use software coming from research environments, or similarly, from open source communities, given the need to perform

extensive (and expensive) safety and security validation and certification activities activities, in fail-safe contexts.

This situation is gradually evolving, for two reasons:

1) the research community itself is evolving, with many researchers and academics now coming from mission-critical industries where they have gained considerable experience in all of the phases of software development, and in particular the needs for certification. Their research is now evolving even to focus often on the thorniest issues of certification (e.g., in machine learning applications in transport), so that large industries are beginning to see real uses for research results in their workflows that take them from implementation through to certification.

2) the trustworthiness of open source software is being reaffirmed in many sectors now, with the help of national organisations, so that large industrial organisations are beginning to break the taboo and are setting up open source programme offices.

We recommend that large industrial organisations try to get ahead of this trend, which is still in its infancy at this time, but we believe it is destined to grow. In Europe in particular, researchers are spending more and more time in industry before moving to academia and have much more to offer private industry than previously, and industry needs to change its mindset in this regard.

Analogously, enough time has passed since open source took hold (well over twenty years), and some open source codebases are firmly established even in large company development programmes. This, too, is destined to grow as the popular codebases demonstrate their trustworthiness in the field over the years. The companies who discard previous prejudices about open source can gain considerable competitive advantage from embracing this emerging trend.

From experience, some key issues for the private sector are also related to:

- 1) Security concerns with respect to open source software
- 2) Financial viability of the software (cost, time, human resources)
- 3) Reliability aspects
- 4) Addressing regulatory requirements (most efficient, cost effective, not impacting operations negatively)
- 5) Skills required

And thus the recommendations naturally fall out of these concerns:

- 1) Ensuring the security of open source software (no back doors or hidden execution).
- 2) Cost effective solutions with a minimal requirement for additional human resource involvement.
- 3) Trust and reliability via controlled testing, certification, etc.
- 4) GDPR and other legal requirements addressed with third party verification.
- 5) Education and skills development should be part of the package.

5.2.4 Private Sector SMEs specific conclusions / requirements

The SMEs are focusing mostly on services and industry. Some of them develop and sell software with their own in-house team and/or outsourcing in EU/ Asia.

Software developers in the private sector SMEs have little time and little resources to join such a membership-based support organizational structure, however, key elements include, but are not limited to:

- 1) Networking opportunities for collaboration
- 2) Educational possibilities
- 3) Commercial elements (looking for new business)
- 4) Funding for projects
- 5) Direct financial funding for the SMEs

SMEs, however, are ideally positioned to join communities involved in the development of open source software. Open source software is in many ways a perfect match to the SME mindset and position in the overall software development ecosystem. The high cost of proprietary software products often closes SMEs out of opportunities for offering consultancy and product development services with these products – whereas open source does not have this problem. Likewise, given that many SMEs are positioned as consultancies and bespoke application developers, active participation in open source communities provides, as one of its primary benefits, the rapid and efficient transfer of knowledge about the latest best practices, technologies, and methodologies. Indeed, most of the dominant software development techniques and methodologies (e.g., agile, DevOps) emerged from SME and consulting contexts.

We recommend that SMEs participate actively (that is, with active contributions also on company time) in multiple open source communities. Certainly, there is a downside: the need to become acquainted with multiple technologies and systems. However, for most SMEs (except those involved in a vendor-specific area such as certain CRM systems), this strategy will render the SME maximally vendor-independent and flexible with respect to the range of projects and consultancies in which it can be involved. In addition, it will provide an automatic “continuing education” to the personnel, which would otherwise be both expensive and time-consuming to achieve using traditional channels.

5.2.5 Public Sector specific conclusions / requirements

Public administrations have an increasingly important role to play in the software landscape, both as customers and as promoters / protectors of their respective software industries at the European, national, and local levels.

The role of the public administration as a customer has grown nearly exponentially over the last decade with the push to digitalization of government services – e.g., the “one-stop shop” for citizen documentation of all kinds, the fluid interchange across borders of administrative data, and internal efficiency of government agencies themselves. Public administrations are learning how to improve in terms of procurement, given the need for adherence to ever more demanding constraints in order to achieve the levels of harmonization (e.g., across both administrative and geographical borders) needed for the kind of sophisticated interoperability of systems that governments are now demanding.

While different research programs such as H2020 in its societal challenge 6 have included research and innovation actions to apply emerging and disruptive technologies in the public sector, the public sector still lags behind.

The digitization of the public sector is also on top of the agendas of most European governments, that however, in a great percentage, are procured by system integrators and software development centers. While in some cases, the software development is industrialized and there exists guidelines and certifications to procure such services, the developed software is still artisanal in most cases. Furthermore, the public sector still uses, to a greater extent, the waterfall model for the larger phases (e.g. analysis, design, development and maintenance) and agile methods for the development itself. DevOps practices and philosophy are becoming more and more common, but a large degree of automation is still to be achieved.

One way of achieving this level of improvement in procurement initiatives is for a public administration to develop a certification / qualification procedures for its suppliers, in order to ensure the level of maturity and skill sets necessary to achieve modern goals of administrations. An example of this would be the Basque Government, who requires its providers' personnel for the development of eGovernment services to be certified under different profiles (e.g. analyst, developer) [41] in the common development framework that the Basque Government has created.

As promoters of their respective constituents in private industry, public administrations have an increasingly important role to play as influencers of policy with respect to the use of open source software (and hardware, too, although that is not in the scope of this specific report). At the European level, the Commission has already spoken out about the advantages for the European software industry of a vibrant open source community, and it has been noted that many of the innovations in open source have originated in Europe.

The specific motivations for public administrations to engage with open source have been extensively studied and have been summarized recently by Fraunhofer ISI and OpenForum Europe.

Economic concerns. These include cost savings, as in the private sector. But these also include switching costs from different vendors, and potential network effect. Vendor lock-in also tends to induce underproduction of public goods. And finally, at a more macro level, concerns include market competition and technology neutrality from the perspective of the public administration.

Technical concerns. Against the background of the earlier discussion on the ambitious national and supra-national projects currently being undertaken by the public administrations, open source naturally addresses many of the most pressing technical concerns. Compatibility is well addressed, in contrast to severe compatibility problems with different vendors. Customizability is a critical requirement across public administrations, nearly impossible to guarantee with proprietary software. And finally, extreme requirements on localization capabilities (e.g., the 27 EU languages) are met by far more open source codebases than by proprietary products, given the broad international natures of the open source communities.

Political concerns. Digitalization of the public sector has already been mentioned as an important political concern. Others include independence from vendors, and even from other governmental bodies.

Legal concerns. There are mounting legal problems with proprietary software and digital products. Consider only the recent controversy over restricting access to 5G products of certain nations because of trade disputes. Software piracy is another legal area that is increasingly difficult to manage with proprietary products, but not so with open source.

Given the considerations above, we recommend that public administrations increase their engagement in open source initiatives. One particular recommendation is to set up an "open source office", for which there are now many examples readily available in public administrations around Europe for guidance.

We also recommend Public Administrations to foster innovative and emerging technologies in their digitization process as they can be caterers for innovation, not only in respect to the services offered to the citizen, but also in respect to the development of software itself.

5.3 The Future Landscape Report 2

The second Landscape Report will include the results of the extensive interviews that will be conducted directly with the stakeholder software developer community and it will also include feedback from the software developers that are participating in the SWForum workshops, conferences and seminars that we are conducting. Depending on these results of the interview, it is possible that another questionnaire may be launched focused on the projects or on specific stakeholders.

It is already foreseen that the **Second SwForum.eu Workshop** will be focused on the research challenges, collaboration, and coordination in European Software Engineering projects. It aims at discussing some contemporary problems such as engagement between research and industry, cross-fertilisation, and bringing together the diverse European Software communities.

Further inputs by the community on research challenges are of particular importance to be discussed.

During the landscapes expected evolution, where the subject is a supported EC project and sufficient self-analysis by the project has occurred we will provide a summary of the radar analysis relevant to that project, i.e. its sector, segment and ring. The project information card in the Radar will provide a technical summary of the project, its radar location information and any further analysis such as MTRL metadata.

Furthermore, the Report 2 will also look at additional model organisations that may not have been included in this Landscape Report. Finally, as needs and requirements are also evolving (for example in new technology development and even cybersecurity), there could be additional elements to be added on top of those noted in this report.

Ultimately, we can introduce the best practices and technology transfer opportunities to cross-synergise European excellence.

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7 APPENDICES

7.1 APPENDIX 1: Questionnaire – Profiling the Stakeholders for the Landscape

1) What is the primary product or service of your organisation?

- product(s) (including components, systems, etc)
- system(s) integration
- software / firmware
- services
- other (please specify)

2) Where is your organisation based?

- EU Member State (which one)
- Europe outside the EU (which one)
- North America (where)
- Asia (where)
- Other (where)

3) What kind of organisation do you come from?

- private sector industrial
- private sector services
- research institute (which focus)
- academic institution (which focus)
- SME (industrial or services which one)

4) Do you develop or sell software with your offering? And if so, how is this done?

- In-house team
- Outsourcing in the EU (where)
- Outsourcing in Europe (where)
- Outsourcing in Asia (where)
- Outsourcing in North America (where)
- Outsourcing elsewhere (where)
- Buy directly someone else's software (where)

5) What type of software do you develop and/or use?

- Proprietary
- Open source
- Combination
- Other (describe)

6) What are your organisation's greatest current concerns? (Rank these - choose as many as you wish)

- Sales
- Financing
- Development of new products / software / service
- Maintaining products / software
- Customer Service
- Regulatory issues

7) Does your organisation belong to any associations or clusters which support your organisation's greatest concerns and which issues are addressed? (Multiple answers are possible)

- Industry lobbying (which association / cluster)
- New projects and innovation funding (which association / cluster)
- Partnering opportunities (which association / cluster)
- Tender and call for proposal monitoring (which association / cluster)

7.2 APPENDIX 2: Questionnaire – Private sector (industrial +SME)

Profiling

* What kind of organisation do you come from?

- Private sector industrial
- Research institute
- Academic institution
- SME
- Public Administration

* Where is your organisation based?

- EU Member State
- Europe outside the EU
- North America
- Other

Questionnaire for the private sector (Industrial +SMEs)

* What is the primary product or service of your organisation?

- Product(s) (including components, systems, etc)
- System(s) integration
- Software / firmware
- Services
- Other

* Please specify

* Do you develop or sell software with your offering?

- Yes
- No

* If so, how is this done?

- In-house team
- Outsourcing in the EU
- Outsourcing in Europe
- Outsourcing in Asia
- Outsourcing in North America
- Outsourcing elsewhere
- Buy directly someone else's software

* For which sector?

* What type of software do you develop and/or use?

- Proprietary
- Open Source

* Which type of open source software do you use/develop?

- Tools
- Office
- Infrastructure
- Web

* Do you use a methodology for software development and operation?

- Waterfall
- Iterative
- Agile
- DevOps
- Other

* If you use third party open source software, which are the main issues / concerns?

- Security
- Not maintained
- Quality
- Documentation
- Other
- I don't use third party software

What are your organisation's greatest current concerns about software development and operation?

* Automation of the processes	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
* Skills	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
* Financial viability	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
* Regulatory issues	★ ★ ★ ★ ★
* Bad tool support	★ ★ ★ ★ ★

* What are the characteristics of trustworthy software for your organization?

- Reliable
- Stable
- Frequently Updated
- Others

* Does your organisation belong to any associations or clusters which support your organisation's greatest concerns and which issues are addressed?

- Yes
- No

* Which ones?

- Industry lobbying
- New projects and innovation funding
- Partnering opportunities
- Tender and call for proposal monitoring
- Other

* Is your company (developers) part of any OS community?

- Yes
- No

* Which one/s?

* Is your company promoting the participation of the company developers in open source community (i.e. extra incentives)?

- Yes
- No

* Are you organizationally accredited with e.g. standards?

- ISO/IEC 27000
- ISO 9000
- No
- Other

Submit

7.3 APPENDIX 3: Questionnaire – Academia (research institute + Academic institution)

Profiling

* What kind of organisation do you come from?

- Private sector industrial
- Research institute
- Academic institution
- SME
- Public Administration

* Which focus?

* Where is your organisation based?

- EU Member State
- Europe outside the EU
- North America
- Other

* Which country?

* Do you believe that open source software is as important as proprietary software?

- Yes
- No

* Why?

* Do you have ongoing open source software research projects?

- Yes
- No

Could you please specify the project names and websites?

Questionnaire for Academia

* In which domains do you expect to see the most research interest going forward?

* What is currently missing in most software engineering / technologies research agendas?

- Cybersecurity
- Supply Chain
- Certification
- Standardisation
- Software Development Lifecycle (SDLC)
- Operation of software
- Others

* Which ones?

* In your opinion, which compliance issues are most difficult to address?

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- No "back doors" / vulnerabilities
- Cybersecurity
- Quality metrics
- Others
- Not applicable

* Which ones?

Which compliance issues (if any) are interesting from the research point of view?

Submit

7.4 APPENDIX 4: Questionnaire – Public administration

Profiling

* What kind of organisation do you come from?

- Private sector industrial
- Research institute
- Academic institution
- SME
- Public Administration

* Where is your organisation based?

- EU Member State
- Europe outside the EU
- North America
- Other

* Which country?

Questionnaire for Public Administrations

* What is your policy on the use of open source software?

* Do you have a formal plan in place for digital transformation?

- Yes
 No

* Which digital infrastructures does your organisation use for its services?

* What do you see as the biggest software challenges to be resolved in public administrations?

* Do you have any applications using disruptive technologies?

- Yes
 No

* If yes, which one/s?

- Artificial Intelligence
 Big Data
 Chatbot
 Cloud Computing
 Data Governance
 Digital Public Services
 Other

* Do you have a formal procurement plan for software?

- Yes
 No

* How was this plan developed?

* In your procurement, do you specify that the developers have to be certified?

- Yes
 No

* Which certification?

* Do you require the software procured to be General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant or does your organisation address the GDPR compliance issues?

- Organisation
 Software Provider

* If your organisation does this, do you use external support?

- Yes
 No

* Do you require your contractors to develop software under a specific methodology?

- Yes
 No

* Which one?

- Waterfall
 Iterative
 Agile
 DevOps
 Other

* At which level is your administration?

- European
 National
 Local

Submit